

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Consolidated outcomes of TransformAr: Innovation Packages

Deliverable 6.5

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Europe is facing an increasing prevalence and risk of climate disasters like extreme weather events and floods. The goal of this report is to consolidate the work done in the EU Horizon 2020 project TransformAr, one of the first research projects that support the implementation of the EU adaptation mission. TransformAr is spearheading transformational adaptation in Europe by spotlighting adaptation solutions and pathways.

TransformAr has successfully resulted in so-called 'Innovation Packages' (IP's) across six demonstrator regions (and 1 replicator region), bolstering climate resilience across diverse communities. Solutions were designed and implemented in 6 demonstrator regions and 1 replicator region: the city of Lappeenranta (Finland), the West Country Region (UK), the Guadeloupe Archipelago (Outermost region, France), Galicia (coastal, Spain), Oristano coastal region (Italy), the city of Egaleo (Greece) and the city of Gjøvik (Norway; replicator of Lappeenranta, Finland).

The Innovation Packages encompass a diverse portfolio of solutions, spanning Nature-based Solutions (NbS), data technologies, innovative governance and financing models. The Innovation Packages also include open-access climate data services and user-friendly tools, significantly enhancing adaptation efforts. In short, this report describes the outcomes of TransformAr, hereby giving an overview of the approaches, tools, and actionable adaptive solutions that are part of the 'Innovation Packages'

The Innovation Packages are structured along the steps of the [Regional Adaptation Support Tool](#) (RAST). The RAST describes 6 practical guidance steps for developing and implementing adaptation solutions, intending to assist local and regional authorities with climate change adaptation strategies and plans: (1) Preparing the ground for adaptation, (2) Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities, (3) Identifying adaptation options, (4) Assessing and selection adaptation options, (5) Implementing adaptation policies and actions, and (6) Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning. Step by step, the report describes the relevant methods used and developed by TransformAr, providing examples from the actionable solutions that were implemented in the project's demonstrators.

Step 1 describes the foundational groundwork for adaptation, which in TransformAr entailed studying the (geographical, environmental, ...) context and engaging the right stakeholders for the co-innovation process. The [Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines](#) and [Best Practices for Change Management](#) can serve as guidelines for involving the right stakeholders and keeping them engaged.

In step 2, climate risks and vulnerabilities of regions are assessed. Within TransformAr, [Climate Impacts Online Europe](#), an online tool to study climate change impacts across Europe, was developed. The tool allows users to select regions and parameters of interest across five sectors (health, climate, socioeconomic, water and agriculture), presented in maps and graphs. In addition, risk indices that allow prioritizing certain regions over others, were developed based on biophysical damages and socio-economic assessments.

After assessing the risks, the RAST steps recommend identifying adaptation options (step 3). In TransformAr, this proceeded through a co-creation process in which adaptation pathways have developed through a stepwise procedure, named the [Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook](#). The Playbook is available as a visual PDF document and also made more easily accessible through a [digital platform](#). TransformAr's [Catalogue Tool](#) provides an overview of adaptation solutions, which served as inspiration for the co-creation workshops. When translating ideas into actionable solutions, one can use TransformAr's [Toolkit for Adaptive Action Planning](#). The application of the Playbook and the Toolkit for Adaptive Action Planning resulted in the Adaptation Pathways per demonstrator, which have been further developed into demonstrator specific Adaptation Action Plans. The findings are described in the [Compendium of Pathways and Action Plans for the demonstrators \(D3.9\)](#).

Also methodologies have been developed for the ex-ante evaluations of solutions (step 4). For a holistic approach, the project used an array of assessment methods addressing different impacts and indicators

of success: public acceptance through [discrete choice experiments](#), [avoided damages and benefits](#), the transformative nature of the solution through a [scorecard tool](#), a valuation of social, environmental and monetary costs and benefits ([D3.6; The Nature Smart Cities Business Model](#)), sustainability through the [Sustainability Rating Method](#), and [energy and water models](#).

Under step 5 of the RAST (implementation), the large variety of solutions implemented in TransformAr's demonstrators are described along with a presentation of key challenges and learnings. Five solution types are distinguished: 1) Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, 2) Governance schemes, 3) Nature-based Solutions, 4) Digital and technological solutions, and 5) Insurance and financial solutions. Some key outcomes are TransformAr's learning stories per solution category ([D4.1](#), [D4.2](#), [D4.3](#), [D4.4](#), [D4.5](#)), and the Catalogue of Solutions ([D6.5; not available yet](#)) providing clear overviews and experiences with implementing the adaptation solutions. Summaries of TransformAr's solutions written by the demonstrators can also be found on [Climate Innovation Window](#). In addition, the [Replicability Assessment Tool](#) is developed with the aim to evaluate the potential for replication of a solution. The Replicability Assessment Tool enables decision-makers and project developers to identify the most viable solutions for replication. Finally, the finance schemes and workshops to engage investors described in Section 5.7 support the financing of solutions. The upcoming bankability reports ([D5.5; not available yet](#)) describe potential finance schemes and workshops held with financial stakeholders.

The last RAST step entails Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning to assess the effectiveness, sustainability, and scalability of climate adaptation solutions. In TransformAr, a [monitoring framework](#) was used which included indicator selection, defining pre-intervention reference points through a baseline data collection, continuous data gathering and data integration and visualization. Depending on the data type, different evaluation methods can be used (e.g., organizational process indicators, life-cycle assessment, field monitoring). A prime example of monitoring in TransformAr were the monitoring systems used to gather in-situ data on for example, storm water levels.

This report concludes with several key learnings and challenges applicable to multiple RAST steps throughout the TransformAr project.

1. TransformAr emphasizes co-innovation through continuous stakeholder engagement across all adaptation steps, using tools like workshops, interviews, and the Playbook to co-create solutions and secure financing. However, maintaining long-term stakeholder participation remains challenging due to fatigue, which can be mitigated by ensuring clear goals, co-benefits, and efficient use of participants' time.
2. Adaptation tools must be both standardized for cross-regional use and flexible enough to fit local contexts, requiring tailored communication and socio-economic assessments.
3. Data availability and integration are major challenges in evaluating adaptation solutions, as local authorities often lack the capacity to collect and manage necessary data for monitoring impacts.
4. The set of indicators and targets needed to measure the impact of a solution on climate change adaptation, or more broadly climate resilience is mostly not specified in the regions, and thus developed in TransformAr on an experimental basis. Early selection of indicators and use of digital tools can support effective data tracking, making it essential to establish systems for data collection from the outset.
5. Successful adaptation planning requires realistic alignment with local resources and ongoing involvement from diverse stakeholders, including for post-implementation maintenance and evaluation. Capacity-building efforts, such as innovative funding schemes and local investment initiatives, are key to sustaining long-term adaptation impact.

With this report, we hope to inform other policymakers and researchers about TransformAr's tools and examples, with the goal of inspiring future replication and improvement, and therefore contribute to Europe's climate change adaptation mission.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Italy)
DCE	Discrete Choice Experiment
E3M	E3 Modelling (Greece)
IPs	Innovation Packages
KCS	Key Community System
KER	Key Exploitable Results
NBS	Nature-based solution
PIK	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (Germany)
RSP	Regional Specific Portfolio
TA	Transformational Adaptation
RAST	Regional Adaptation Support Tool
NCSR	National Centre of Scientific Research Demokritos (Greece)
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust (UK)

0.0 Introduction

Europe is facing an increasing prevalence and risk of climate disasters like extreme weather events and floods. Short-term, incremental solutions are no longer sufficient. We need transformational adaptation, which refers to “actions aiming at adapting to climate change resulting in significant changes in structure or function that go beyond adjusting existing practices.” (IPCC, 2022). In this light, TransformAr aims to demonstrate solutions and pathways, deemed essential for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching transformational adaptation (TA). Solutions were designed and implemented in 6 demonstrator regions and 1 replicator region: Lappeenranta (Finland), West Country Region (UK), Guadeloupe (France), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Egaleo (Greece) and Gjøvik (Norway; replicator of Lappeenranta, Finland). For ease of reference, we call all seven of them demonstrators. In addition, the project developed methods and tools relevant to the entire transformational adaptation process from setting up the right environment (e.g., involving stakeholders) and designing solutions, to implementation, evaluation and acceleration of the solutions.

This deliverable aims to consolidate the work done in TransformAr in “Innovation Packages” (IPs). The IPs are designed to enhance communities' resilience to social and climate challenges and provide a structured process that includes user-friendly climate data services, practical solutions, and clear pathways to help communities adapt to climate change impacts such as droughts, floods, and pollution. To ensure long-term success and scalability, the approach emphasizes community engagement, the integration of local stakeholder knowledge, and bottom-up strategies. Furthermore, demonstrating both public and private benefits will be key to attracting future investment and support. The Innovation Packages will follow the structure of the [Regional Adaptation Support Tool](#) (RAST) to be in line with the European adaptation mission, while referring to actionable solutions implemented in the TransformAr demonstrators. The RAST describes 6 practical guidance steps for developing and implementing adaptation solutions, intending to assist local and regional authorities with climate change adaptation strategies and plans.

Key definitions

Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) = A set of 6 steps that describe the process of climate change adaptation planning, from development and implementation to monitoring and evaluation.

Innovation Packages (IPs) = A consolidation of TransformAr's approaches, tools, and actionable adaptive solutions, per step of the RAST framework. A bundle of products and services regions or communities need to develop and drive their transformational adaptation process.

0.1 Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST) steps

The process to reach transformational adaptation can be divided into **6 steps**, according to the EU mission's framework “Regional Adaptation Support Tool” (Figure 1): Preparing the ground for adaptation, assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities, identifying adaptation options, assessing and selecting adaptation options, implementing adaptation policies and actions, and monitoring, evaluation and learning. The steps offer methodologies to develop a transformational adaptation pathway—the primary planning instrument that guides region-specific adaptation processes.

The first step is *Preparing the ground for adaptation (S1)*, which includes establishing political commitment and identifying and engaging stakeholders. Within TransformAr, a specific emphasis was put on the co-innovation process. This refers to involving stakeholders at different levels to co-create the innovative transformational adaptation process. The goal is to make innovation more demand-driven and derive input not only from science, but also from practice and intermediaries, such as public

administration, advisors, businesses, NGOs, and end-users. This co-innovation setup will improve the practical relevance, acceptance and dissemination of solutions.

The second step, *Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities (S2)* consists of identifying and assessing the key indicators and risks, which will be important to prioritize regions. A first objective is to define the most relevant regions, sectors, and communities to target with the transformational adaptation pathway, with the goal of optimal allocation of resources. Second, a full-scale socio-economic impact assessment of climate change and transformational adaptation is conducted and applied to the local scale (in TransformAr's case to the demonstrator scale). It provides insights on climate and socio-economic risks, considering uncertainty on the labour market, inter-industrial spillovers, and distributional impacts.

In the third step, *Identifying adaptation options (S3)*, different adaptation solutions are considered and planned. In TransformAr, this happened through co-construction. Stakeholders design a pathway consisting of quantitative targets and a combination of solutions that respond to prevailing climate risks. TransformAr's [catalogue tool](#) (D3.2) and [playbook](#) (D3.10) can be helpful to guide the process of co-constructing pathways. The targets and solutions are made more concrete in an adaptation planning phase. The goal of adaptation planning is to evaluate investment strategies based on climate risk reduction and economic criteria, using a real options approach.

Assessing and selecting adaptation options (S4) is the next step. Collecting and combining information on the solutions, solutions should be selected and combined into a region-specific portfolio to maximize expected impacts and benefits. In this stage, ex-ante impact assessments are conducted to compare the public acceptance, impact, costs and benefits of different solution packages. An example is the [assessment](#) that was done for the case of Lappeenranta (D3.6).

After assessing and selecting solutions, it is time for the *Implementation of adaptation policies and actions (S5)*. TransformAr's solutions may be categorized in different types: Nature-based solutions (NBS), Technological and digital solutions, Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, Governance schemes, and Insurance, financial and economics schemes. They are first tested and validated at the regional level, and may then be implemented at a larger scale, which requires viable financing models.

In the final RAST step, *Monitoring, evaluation and learning (MEL) (S6)*, the impact and effectiveness of solutions are evaluated. Accurate assessment of solution performance is an important requisite to demonstrate the environmental goods and services generated as well as the ownership by the community, and therefore their long-term sustainability.

Figure 1 Visualisation of the Regional Adaptation Support Tool steps (Ss) of the transformational adaptation process. Source: [Regional Adaptation Support Tool](#).

0.2 Actionable Adaptive Solutions

Within TransformAr, a variety of adaptation solutions have been developed and implemented in 6 demonstrators and 1 replicator. These may be regarded as examples for future replication in other regions. Throughout these IPs, the demonstrator regions and solutions will be relied upon as examples and referenced where relevant. All solutions fall within five categories: Nature-based solutions (NBS), Technological and digital solutions, Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, Governance schemes, and Insurance, financial and economics schemes. Table 1 provides an overview of the demonstrators, the main risks they face, their solutions and the category the solution belongs to. Summaries of TransformAr’s solutions written by the demonstrators can also be found in TransformAr’s Catalogue of Solutions (D6.3; *not available yet*) and on [Climate Innovation Window](#).

Table 1 Demonstrators and actionable adaptive solutions.

Demonstrator	Main risks	Solution	Category	
Lappeenranta, Finland	Flooding	Crowdsourcing Citizen App (CAF)	Awareness-raising and Behavioural Change	
		Urban run-off system (URB)	Nature-Based Solutions	
	The spread of harmful substances into water bodies (water pollution)	Stormwater Monitoring and Modular System (SWMM)	Digital and Technological Solutions	
		Reduction of diversity of urban nature	Choice Experiment (CEI)	Insurance Schemes and Financial Solutions
Gjovik, Norway (replicator of Lappeenranta)	Same as Lappeenranta	Crowdsourcing Citizen App (CAF)	Awareness-raising and Behavioural Change	
		Stormwater Monitoring and Modular System (SWMM)	Digital and Technological Solutions	
		Choice Experiment (CEI)	Insurance Schemes and Financial Solutions	
West Country Region, UK	Extreme weather events due to hotter, drier summers and warmer, wetter winters	Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW)	Nature-Based Solutions	
		Integrated Constructed Wetlands Monitoring (ICWM)	Digital and Technological Solutions	
	Reduced water quality and water scarcity	Payment for Ecosystem Services (GB) – renamed to ‘nutrient credit schemes’	Insurance Schemes and Financial Solutions	
Guadeloupe, France	Increasing prevalence of weather events, such as floods and hurricanes due to changing temperature	Nudging (NUDG) to reduce water consumption by tourists	Awareness-raising and Behavioural Change	
		Adaptation fund (AF)	Insurance Schemes and Financial Solutions	
Galicia, Spain	Coastal flooding/ extreme weather events	Resilience Index (RI)	Governance Schemes	
		Vulnerability of the aquaculture and shellfish harvesting sector	Mussel-Raft Monitoring (MRM)	Digital and Technological Solutions
		Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)	Digital and Technological Solutions	
Oristano, Italy	Extreme weather causing floods and droughts	Coastal Contracts (COAST)	Governance Schemes	
		Smart Grid and Gates (SG)	Nature-Based Solutions	

	Impact on aquaculture and agriculture sectors		
Egaleo, Greece	Extreme weather-related events (floods, droughts wildfires,..) Socioeconomic vulnerabilities	Citizen App Engagements (CAE)	Awareness-raising and Behavioural Change
		Awareness-raising modules (AWAR)	Awareness-raising and Behavioural Change
		Demand analysis for social services/ infrastructure (DSI)	Governance Schemes
		Climate Innovation Hub (CIH)	Governance Schemes
		Smart Climate Stations (SCS)	Digital and Technological Solutions
All	/	Insurance schemes	Insurance and Financial Solutions

0.3 Innovation Packages

To consolidate the work done in this project, and provide a guide for potential replicators, *Innovation Packages* (IPs) are created. The IPs combine the RAST steps and the actionable solutions implemented by TransformAr's demonstrators (Table 1). The IPs go through the steps one by one (Sections 1 to 6), describing the relevant tools and practices that can be replicated, while providing examples from TransformAr's demonstrators. This results in solutions, products, and services that can support future regions and communities in their transformational adaptation. By following the described process, any European territory can initiate and sustain its adaptation process.

1.0 Step 1: Preparing the ground for adaptation

Step 1 is all about laying the groundwork, establishing partnerships, and demonstrating the political commitment needed to create solutions. **Co-innovation** plays an important role. Relevant stakeholders should be brought together to co-create the process and solutions. By involving not only governmental bodies but also companies, NGOs, and citizens, the solutions will be more practically relevant, more accepted, and more easily disseminated.

The co-innovation process is relevant from the start to the end of an adaptation pathway or project. This aligns with the values of the Multi-Actor Approach—a framework that TransformAr helped validate beyond its original field of application—which emphasizes the challenge of creating viable solutions within viable communities. The Multi-Actor Approach, as stimulated by several Horizon 2020 calls and the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2021-2024) (European Commission, 2021), refers to “bringing the right people together from science, practice, or anyone who can help tackle the objective of the project. All experience and knowledge are therefore taken into account and the partners create results together, to answer real problems” (EIP-AGRI, 2017, p. 3). Not only was TransformAr’s co-innovation process the trigger for the regional portfolios of climate adaptation by the six demonstrators, it was also meant to assess the potential of replicable, collaborative methodologies and practices. By remaining coherent to this mindset, TransformAr was positioned to share, evaluate and perfect the co-innovation process.

As described further down, the co-innovation process consists of three distinct outputs with replicable methods and tools: the stakeholder engagement methodology, and the lessons learnt package.

1.1 Stakeholder engagement methodology

TransformAr selected 6 demonstrators (and 1 replicator) facing common water-related challenges to construct, test, and validate the potential of co-innovation processes for Transformational Adaptation (TA) towards climate resilience in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. The 6 demonstrators, for short, represent a variety of territorial scales as well as situations regarding societal readiness to climate change across the EU -including overseas territories-. The set up of the Innovation Ecosystems was based on a community or an administrative jurisdiction that collaborated in creating conditions for co-creation and testing of actionable solutions for transformation adaptation: these were the city of Lappeenranta (Finland), the West Country Region (the UK), the Guadeloupe archipelago (France), the Galicia region (Spain), the Oristano Gulf coastal area (Italy) and the municipality of Egaleo (Greece). The identified key community systems, separated by up to 8.500 km, are depicted in Figure 2.

For each demonstrator, the general context was studied, and an overview of geographic, social and economic information was created ([D1.1](#)). It also shed light on the territory’s climate vulnerability, existing adaptation-relevant policy plans, as well as response measures increasing the adaptive capacity of the demonstrator in question. Report D1.1 also introduces key actors that play a role in accelerating adaptation efforts via a stakeholders’ matrix developed for each demonstrator, defining the influence of the territory’s actors and their role and their motivation to develop and implement transformational climate adaptation measures.

Figure 3 TransformAr’s Key Community Systems (from: [Deliverable 1.1](#))

Figure 2 TransformAr Stakeholder Matrix typology (from: [Deliverable 1.2](#))

Throughout the process of analysing the general context, it is important to map the key stakeholders. To follow the multi-actor approach, it is advised to involve local actors not as a study object, but with the goal of using their skills and perspective to ensure the viability of solutions developed alongside them. This ensures quick adoption and upkeep. Within TransformAr, citizens, end-users, and agents that could influence the solutions were screened in [Deliverable 1.2](#), the Matrix of Key Stakeholders. Figure 3 shows a comprehensive overview of stakeholders to be involved in the process, as established through the TransformAr project.

Alongside identifying the main stakeholders, a tailor-made methodology to drive the co-creation process with regional communities and relevant stakeholders was developed: the [Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines](#). This entails the expression of the multi-actor approach in procedural and governance terms, for an overview, see Figure 4. The aim was to trigger interactive innovation across the whole value chain, tackling demand-driven, actual needs of the aforementioned actors, supporting the adoption of the participatory framework and their harmonised development. To that end, each Innovation Ecosystem was split into a geographical and a technical dimension, balancing their governance.

Figure 4 The Multi-Actor Approach mindset for co-innovation (adapted from [D1.1](#))

The Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines consist of a 4-step operational flow regarding the involvement of stakeholders, shown in Figure 5: Stakeholders Mapping and Identification (using the Matrix of Figure 3), Planning the Engagement Activities, Design and Implementation of Engagement Activities with Stakeholders, and Reporting and Follow-up.

Figure 5 Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines - Operational Flow

This groundwork of identifying stakeholders and developing a general methodology to apply the multi-actor approach fed into TransformAr's co-creation process, formalised in the [Adaptive Pathways](#)

[Transformation Playbook](#). Further elaboration on the Playbook is given in Section 3 on identifying adaptation options (step 3 of the RAST).

1.2 Lessons learnt package

Throughout additional studies on the demonstrator's performance during the co-innovation process, dynamically evolving together with the Playbook, the engagement methodology was validated and best practices and transversal exchanges within the co-innovation process were identified.

A novel [coding system](#) that helped produce the analysis of the implications of attitudes and beliefs towards the solutions preidentified in TransformAr was developed (D1.4). This also includes a protocol for Focus Group implementation so that replicators can expand on this line of research.

In addition, six best practices and transversal exchanges between demonstrators were consolidated in deliverables [D1.5](#), [D1.6](#), and D1.7 (*not available yet*) and visualized. These pieces allowed for further specialisation of the demonstrators and more informed decisions in the allocation of resources while maintaining a coherent project vision. As the project advanced, the demonstrators also held monthly meetings together to share information and better coordinate geographically and technically.

Figure 6 Best practices for Change Management (from: [D1.5](#))

With the Innovation Ecosystems balanced and the solution co-creation in full swing, an EU-level Community of Practice that could provide networking and technical assistance for the project's stakeholders was created. It was a welcome coincidence that the European Commission also wanted to see this kind of network set up and was looking to the Green Deal and Mission Adaptation projects as the main drivers.

The TransformAr consortium complemented this idea with its Climate Change Adaptation Network, with sister projects [Regilience](#), [Arsinoe](#), and [Impetus](#), to make coordinated insights, contributing to the different Thematic Working Groups of this community of practice, while also creating capacity development workshops. Figure 7 depicts the conclusions from the Thematic Working Group on Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement.

Key Messages – engaging citizens in Climate Adaptation

Figure 7 Conclusions from the Thematic Working Group on Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement

As a result of the feedback of stakeholders, local partners, and facilitators (e.g., Mission Adaptation and the Sustainable Development Solutions Network), it was clear that the initial engagement methodology needed additional measures to avoid fatigue without compromising either the regional portfolios or the Innovation Packages overall. Aside from bundled activities and joint decision-making, each demo required tailored follow-up actions and more flexible reporting.

To overcome barriers to the implementation of the action plans and incentivise the engagement of stakeholders in the upkeep of the solutions, the demonstrators also validated the use of systems thinking and scenario exploration. Said capacities were developed in the context of the consultation workshops-complementary activities to the conclusions of the action plans that aided in creating a common agenda and identifying the knowledge owners for an extended portfolio of solutions. All these case studies and methodological considerations will be included in Deliverable 1.3, the upcoming final report on stakeholder engagement activities from TransformAr. As with the best practices, this document is styled as a lessons learnt showcase, focused on replication instead of creating an artificial, fit-for-all scheme for co-creation governance and innovation ecosystem setup.

2.0 Step 2: Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities

Step 2 entails the identification of the most important risks and key indicators, which will feed into a socio-economic impact assessment. This supports the prioritisation of regions for climate adaptation.

2.1 Climate change impacts

Studying climate change impacts on various sectors and under different scenarios is vital to know where, to what extent, and which climate change adaptation solutions are necessary. Within the TransformAr project, PIK developed a portal that provides easy access to climate impacts on various sectors in Europe: [Climate Impacts Online Europe](#). The data provided in the portal are results of TransformAr, based on climate scenario data of the project [ISIMIP](#). They are described in [Deliverable 2.2](#) of the project. The global model runs were regionalized to a 50 km x 50 km grid and bias-adjusted. A major advantage of the ensemble is the use of the latest generation of global climate models and greenhouse gas concentration scenarios.

Over the project runtime, it became obvious that the project partners and end users had problems to understand the nature and amount of data available for them, although support was granted within the project by the involved partners. The data availability and description were also a demand from a midterm review. Therefore, it was decided to compile a web portal to visualize and describe the data and methods in maps and graphs and make the available data downloadable in common formats following sections introduces the portal, explains the main functionality, illustrates some of the outputs and discusses further steps.

Figure 8 Starting page of Climate Impacts Online Europe with the five sectors currently included. Access to portal [here](#).

Currently, data of five sectors are considered in the web portal (Figure 8): Climate, Water, Health, Agriculture and Socio-economics. When choosing one of the sectors, sector-specific variables can be selected and analysed.

Figure 9 shows the window that appears when selecting the climate sector. Climate variables such as mean, min and max temperature, precipitation, and derived variables such as continuous hot days, ice days etc. can be selected. On the left under “settings”, selection of scenarios, seasons and aggregation of the results can be chosen. The scale at the bottom is to select the time period. It can also be used to provide the results in a movie-like feature starting from the historical period and running until the end of the century.

Figure 9 The entry page when selecting the sector climate.

The tabs on top provide general information about the project and data, explain the usage and data basis, a glossary, provide educational material, one can select different languages and download the selected data. Available languages up until now are: English, German, French, Spanish and Italian.

Figure 10 provides a typical result when choosing, in this case, mean temperature development for a specific region, here for the entire Europe, and scenario, here SSP5-8.5. The lowest aggregation level for climate is Nuts2¹.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/>

Figure 10 Example of temperature development for a Attica region (where the demonstrator Egaleo, Greece is situated) and SSP scenario.

Download of the selected data can be done in different ways, for example by choosing the “table” button on top of the graph. This way, a summary of the available data for the selected time period is provided. Another possibility is to download the entire time series for a specific region. The data are stored in CSV (comma-separated values) format, easily loadable into all popular programming, text, and table calculation software.

The functionality of the portal is already advanced, but it is meant to be a “living portal”, saying that new information and data from the project partners and beyond will be integrated as soon as they are validated. One of the next steps is to include tourism as another sector. Improvement of the functionality upon feedback and correction of coding problems is a constant task.

The data shows that climate change is ongoing and the impacts on water resources and on vegetation are already visible and will increase with further global warming. Extremes show the same pattern of stronger trends with higher temperature. This is relevant because critical infrastructure is normally adjusted to protect against events of a certain intensity (or return level), and precautionary measures are challenged by the increasing hazards. However, the results also illustrate what we gain if we invest consequently into avoiding greenhouse gases: significantly lower consequences for natural resources and the extremes, and as a result, the environment and the people living in specific regions of Europe will benefit accordingly. Special attention must be paid to the Guadeloupe demonstrator due to its overseas characteristics (less data are available, and a need as formulated by the demonstrator to have more data and information for the territory).

2.2 Risk assessment

Climate change poses significant challenges to economies worldwide, and the European Union (EU) is no exception. With increasing frequency and severity of extreme weather events, rising sea levels, and shifting climatic patterns, the economic implications are profound and multifaceted. Understanding climate risks and costs associated with climate change is crucial for developing effective mitigation and adaptation strategies. Despite relative abundance in climate risk assessments, spanning from local to the regional scale, a common definition of climate change risk is not yet available, with different approaches

followed in the IPCC reports and by national-level assessments, and typically considering combination of hazard, exposure and vulnerability factors to define a climate risk. From the combination of these components, risk severity is estimated using quantitative thresholds of impact. The thresholds are expressed in terms of economic loss (monetary or GDP percentage), affected population or other losses (e.g., land losses, losses of species, loss of historical heritage) and are aimed at making risk magnitude comparable across different systems and impacts. Within TransformAr, a thorough risk assessment was performed, including an assessment of biophysical damages for each sector (D2.3; Section 2.2.1), a socio-economic assessment (D2.4; Section 2.2.2), and the creation and evaluation of risk indices (D2.5 and D2.6; Section 2.2.3). Figure 11 provides an overview of the risk assessment procedure in TransformAr, leading to the risk indices described in 2.2.3. The black dots along the arrows indicate ranking of data to allow comparability; the red dots indicate when the geometric mean of the ranked indicators is computed, with the arrows showing the results.

Figure 11 Schematic representation of the methodology used to derive the risk index from the combination of intermediate impact, socio-economic exposure and vulnerability for each of the studied sectors.

2.2.1 Biophysical Damages

Following the data gathering of the climate change impact tool, biophysical modelling outcomes and other analytical assessments from relevant repositories (e.g., ISIMIP, Climate Data Store of Copernicus) and previous EU projects were aggregated. They were expanded to elaborate those to provide a wider valuation of expenditures linked to climate hazard categories relevant to demonstrators (e.g., river and coastal floods, agriculture, droughts, infrastructure). Such evaluations have been derived and processed to produce and be translated into damage assessments, as specific economic-relevant parameters (e.g., capital stock damage, sectoral productivity reduction, changes in consumption patterns) that could highlight future damages in monetary terms in relation to the historical baseline. The following specific modelling parameters were included: 1) (capital and) land stock damage from river floods; 2) land stock damage from coastal floods; 3) change in agriculture productivity of main crops; 4) change in catch for fishery sectors; 5) change in tourism fluxes, in terms of arrivals and overnight stays, 6) and change in health indicators and labour productivity. Figure 12 offers a visual summary of the data, methods and

metrics used in the damage assessments performed, along with the sources from which they were sourced.

A summary of the evaluations of each sector can be found in [deliverable 2.3](#).

	AGRICULTURE	FISHERIES	TOURISM	RIVER FLOODING	COASTAL FLOODING	HEALTH AND LABOUR
EU-wide Damage Sources	ISIMIP 3b, ISIMIP 2b, COACCH, Orlov et al. (2021), Van Passel et al. (2017)	ISIMIP 3b, ISIMIP 2b, Cheung et al., (2016), COACCH	Matei et al. (2023), Amelung & Moreno (2012); Barrios & Ibáñez (2015)	COACCH, H2020_Insurance, Paprotny et al. (2020), PESETA IV, Dottori et al. (2020)	COACCH Lincke et al. (2019), PESETA IV, Tiggeloven et al. (2020)	ISIMIP 3b climate driver
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Selected Sectorial Impact Modelling Method	<u>ISIMIP 3b</u> : CROVER; CYGMA1p74; EPIC-IIASA; LDNDC; LPJmL; LPJ-GUESS; PEPIC; PROMET; SIMPLACE-LINTULS	<u>ISIMIP 3b</u> : BOATS; EcoOcean	<u>Matei et al.</u> : Tourist Climate Index	<u>COACCH</u> : GLOFRIS, LISFLOOD, CLIMRISK_RIVER <u>TransformAr</u> : SWIM	<u>COACCH</u> : DIVA	<u>TransformAr</u> : wet-bulb globe temperature
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Type of Damage & Damage Metrics at EU Level	Change in crop yield (Tons/ha) and irrigation water requirement (mm/ha)	Change in total catch (g m ⁻²)	Change in tourist fluxes & related demand	Change in Expected Annual Damage on Land Use stock (billion€)	Change in Expected Annual Damage on Land Use stock (billion€)	Change in Comfort & Labour productivity (% full working capacity)

Figure 12 Data, methods and metrics used in the damage assessments, along with the sources from which they were sourced.

2.2.2 Socio-economic assessment

This assessment aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the economic impacts of climate change within the EU, focusing on both direct and indirect costs. By evaluating the financial burden on various sectors and regions, the socio-economic assessment seeks to inform policy decisions and foster resilience against future climate risks.

The analysis builds on relevant literature and explores the macroeconomic implications of specific climate impact chains on the EU regions by employing a large-scale hybrid economic model, GEM-E3-FIT-R. The model follows a two-layer approach: at the top level the peer-reviewed global computable general equilibrium (CGE) assesses the impacts of any given scenario at the national level; while at the bottom-layer, the regional module dynamically disaggregates national-wide projections at the NUTS2 level based on regional specificities and features captured by a single index (the attractiveness index).

The cost estimates are based on the latest outputs of climatic models under the coordinated effort of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), namely CMIP6 that is featured in the 2021 IPCC sixth assessment report (AR6). This implies that the model simulations are based on the most up-to-date estimate of climate costs, describing the cascading effects of specific damages to economic sectors and agents. The analysis does not cover the full spectrum but a selection of climate impacts.

In total 10 different scenarios were quantified based on the type of climate impact, for two climatic variants (RCP2.6 and RCP8.5): i) coastal and river flooding, ii) temperature increases on **crop yields** and fisheries, iii) temperature increase, humidity, precipitation, wind and cloud cover on **tourist arrivals** and iv) temperature increase on **labour productivity** and v) an **aggregate** scenario which examines the combined effect of all previous climatic impacts. Table 2 below presents for each of the individual scenario, the climatic inputs under consideration.

Table 2 Scenario definition and climatic inputs

SCENARIO	SECTOR	VARIABLE	SOURCE
AGR	Agriculture	Change in crop yield in relation to harvested area (%)	ISIMIP 3b (yield); EUROSTAT and SPAM (harvested area)
	Fisheries	Change in total catch (%)	ISIMIP 3b
FLOOD	River flooding	Expected annual damage on Land Use stock (EUR)	SWIM model
	Coastal flooding	Expected annual damage on Land Use stock (EUR)	DIVA model
LAB	Health and Labour	Wet-bulb globe temperature	ISIMIP 3b
TOUR	Tourism	Tourist Climate Index	Matei et al., 2023

Economic and employment impacts are calculated both at the national and at the sub-national (NUTS2) level for EU27 member states for all scenarios defined. In the aggregate scenario, GDP impacts are found to be negative throughout the projection period for most EU27 countries, while the effects aggravate over time. For example, in 2030, GDP changes are found to range from -0.29% (RCP2.6) to -0.34% (RCP8.5) and in 2050 from -0.83% (RCP2.6) to -1.43% (RCP8.5) compared to the reference case. Changes are driven primarily by the effects of floodings and of changes in labor productivity to the economy and to a lesser extent by tourism and changes in yields. More specifically, coastal and river floodings lead to a GDP reduction in 2050 of 0.45% to 0.83%, in RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 respectively, while changes in labor productivity imply additional losses of 0.4% to 0.6%.

Figure 13 EU27 - GDP changes in the aggregate scenario (compared to reference)

At the regional level, we find that impacts are higher for southern European and coastal regions. In terms of the top losing regions in RCP8.5 in 2030, we find that Weser-Ems (DE94), Veneto (ITH3) and Prov. Antwerpen (BE21) record the highest GDP losses of 3.8% and 2.2% respectively while in 2050, Weser-Ems (DE94), Veneto (ITH3) and Ciudad de Ceuda (ES63) record losses of 25%, 9.9% and 9.2% with respect to the reference. In Weser-Ems (DE94) and Prov. Antwerpen (BE21) economic impacts are driven primarily by flooding damage, while in Veneto (ITH3) and Ciudad de Ceuda (ES63) it is the combined effect of floodings and lower labor productivity that determines the overall GDP effects. An interesting finding is that we find shift in the distribution of national sectorial production from coastal regions to insular regions in countries such as Spain and France, and from north to south in Italy.

Figure 14 GDP changes in the aggregate scenario (compared to reference) at the NUTS2 level in 2050

2.2.3 Risk Indices

Regional risk is associated with changes due to climate change. Complementing current literature on risk indexes (e.g., ESPON, Germanwatch, EEA, Notre Dame, ...), two TransformAr modelling teams (CMCC and E3M) each developed a EU27 subnational risk index based on the most recent climatic and socioeconomic data and ranked regions according to their relevant probability of being adversely affected by climate change. These risk assessments provide several advancements compared to other existing evaluations. They rely on the most recent CMIP6 climate model projections and socioeconomic SSP scenarios in line with the latest IPCC AR6 report. Furthermore, based on the different methods tested and used in [D2.5](#) and [D2.6](#), these risk assessments have integrated specific indicator metrics spatially articulated at the NUTS3 level, or characterizing hazards more specifically to the sectoral values through modelling intermediate impacts.

Conceptually, both risk indexes ([D2.5](#) and [D2.6](#)) are based on the (latest) IPCC's 6th Assessment Report (AR6) which defines risk as a combination of elements of exposure, vulnerability, and hazard. Vulnerability is defined as the product of sensitivity and adaptive capacity. However, there are three main differences: i) regional resolution as the risk index in D2.5 is calculated at the NUTS2, while the risk index in D2.6 is calculated at the NUTS3 level, ii) the list of indicators included in the calculation of each pillar and iii) the metric of hazard: in D2.5 (intermediate) hazard is defined as the overall climate change impact on sector-specific values (e.g., yield change for agriculture, bed nights change for tourism), while in D2.6 hazard is defined over changes in one or more climatic indicators (e.g., precipitation levels, number of hot days) that are relevant to the impact chain examined. D2.5 thus provides a more comprehensive

articulation of sectorial impacts, but at coarser resolution (i.e. NUTS2 level), while D2.6 addresses hazard-based impact at NUTS3 resolution. Therefore, the risk assessment from D2.6 may catch spatial detail for more local and case-specific context, while from D2.5 can be used to capture broader sectoral dynamics. Table 3 presents an overview of hazards included in the different risk indices.

Table 3 Hazards included in TransformAr’s two Risk Indices

	D2.5 (CMCC)	D2.6 (E3M)
Hazards	Yield change (%)	Maximum continuous hot days
	Total catch change (%)	Number of hot days (max temperature above 30)
	Bed nights change (%)	Precipitation
	Expected annual damage (€)	Water balance
	Expected annual damage (€)	Water flow
		Number of wet days
		Maximum flow
		Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT)

Both in D2.5 and D2.6 the risk index is calculated for each impact-chain individually and in the end an aggregate risk index is calculated. In total 7 distinctive key economic systems are defined (Table 4), with D2.5 assessing five out of 7 and D2.6 assessing four out of seven.

Table 4 Impact chains studied in TransformAr’s two Risk Indices

	Agriculture	Fisheries	Tourism	Coastal flooding	River flooding	Labor productivity	Water scarcity
D2.5 (CMCC)	•	•	•	•	•		
D2.6 (E3M)	•		•			•	•

With respect to tourism, the 2 indices produce a slightly different pattern of risk. D2.5 results show significantly higher costs in central and north European countries (e.g., in Germany and Poland compared to D2.6 where the risk is relatively smaller. Furthermore, most Spanish and Portuguese regions are classified as low risk in D2.5 and as high/very high risk in D2.6. Such differences are inherent to the different methodologies used by the two risk assessments, particularly by the different hazard components selected. Moreover, the difference mainly emerges comparing the low-emission projections (i.e., RCP2.6 and SSP126), and gets smaller in the high-emission projections, suggesting that inherent uncertainty in the climate projections might also play a role. On the other hand, both studies show that central and south regions in France, coastal regions of Bulgaria and Romania, as well as some Italian regions, face medium to high risk compared to the rest of the EU27 regions.

Regarding agriculture, the scope of the studies differs, as in D2.5, only the impacts in crop yields are considered, and hence the results from the two modelling efforts cannot be directly compared. However, both indices imply higher risk for regions in Spain, Portugal, Italy, and some regions in Croatia compared to the rest of the EU27 regions.

Climate Risk Index - Tourism
RCP2.6 2050

TOURISM SECTOR RISK - SSP126 2050

Climate Risk Index - Tourism
RCP2.6 2050

TOURISM SECTOR RISK - SSP585 2050

Figure 15 Risk indices in the Tourism sector under different scenarios (D2.6 left, D2.5 right)

Climate Risk Index - Agriculture
RCP2.6

AGRICULTURE SECTOR RISK - SSP126 2050

Climate Risk Index - Agriculture
RCP8.5

AGRICULTURE SECTOR RISK - SSP585 2050

Figure 16 Risk indices in the Agricultural sector under different scenarios

Regarding total risk impacts, both models imply a high risk associated with climate change impacts for South European countries (Spain, Italy, Greece), eastern regions of Romania and Bulgaria, and southern Sweden. In D2.5, a coastal pattern is also observed as these regions face a higher risk associated with flooding. Both assessments generally agree on the risk magnitude in most European regions, with small differences appearing locally. The similarity in the aggregated risk estimate produced by the two assessments demonstrates the general reliability of both methodological choices.

Climate Risk Index -Total
RCP2.6

AGGREGATED RISK - SSP126 2050

Climate Risk Index -Total
RCP8.5

AGGREGATED RISK - SSP585 2050

Figure 17 Total risk under different scenarios

3.0 Step 3: Identifying adaptation options

Step 3 builds on the laid groundwork and risk assessments to choose and plan adaptation solutions. In TransformAr, this was done through pathway co-construction and adaptation planning.

3.1 Pathway co-construction

Adaptive pathway co-construction entails the design of a pathway with quantitative targets and a combination of solutions that respond to prevailing climate risks. In TransformAr, an [Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook](#) (from here on 'Playbook') was developed that presents a methodology to guide the co-construction of climate change adaptation pathways by integrating a transformative vision for regions seeking to implement transformative adaptation. As it was tested in the six demonstrators, the Playbook was turned into a [digital platform](#) for easier and widespread adoption. The process helped create a sense of shared ownership of the solutions and thus was indispensable to make the project closer to its ambition of systemic change.

"Climate change adaptation pathways" is an emerging concept used to support decision-making and planning for adaptation to climate change in a context of uncertainty. As defined by Werners et al. (2021) "*adaptation pathways are broadly understood as sequences of actions, which can be implemented progressively, depending on future dynamics*" (see also Figure 18).

Figure 18 Adaptation Pathways Map (from: Zandvoort et al. (2017))

The Playbook is structured into discrete, modular chapters, allowing users to navigate specific sections relevant to their needs. This modularity ensures flexibility and accessibility, making the Playbook a practical resource for a diverse range of users, including public and private entities, and scientific and industrial partners. A cornerstone of the Playbook is the emphasis on engaging local stakeholders through a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) (see also Section 1). Effective stakeholder engagement is vital for the success of transformative adaptation measures.

The Playbook employs a workshop-based methodology involving the relevant stakeholders divided into three main sessions, each with specific objectives and outputs (Figure 19):

- **Session I** focuses on understanding current climate-related challenges and existing solutions. Activities include utilizing canvases to map out hazards, exposure, vulnerability, and socio-economic impacts.
- **Session II** assesses the intermediate impacts of climate change on different sectors, identifying risk levels, indicators, and thresholds to prioritize the most significant risks.
- **Session III** develops a vision for the desired future and aligns adaptation measures with this vision, creating an adaptation pathway map specific to each sector, while outlining solutions to address the most prominent risks.

Figure 19 Adaptation pathways co-creation sequence (from: [D3.10 Playbook](#))

From February 2022 to January 2023, the six demonstrators of the TransformAr project organized workshops to apply this methodology and co-construct adaptation pathways at both territorial and sectoral levels. The same approach may be used by future actors wanting to identify transformational adaptation pathways and solutions.

3.1.1 Session I: Climate perceptions, challenges, and solutions

The first workshop aims to:

- Identify the climate challenges and risks in terms of hazards, exposure, vulnerability, risk, and socio-economic impact.
- Get to know the different participants of the region and their respective challenges.

One of the main outputs of the first session is the design of a “risk chain” based on expert judgement to identify the main climate risk in the region studied. According to the IPCC, the risk refers to the potential for consequences where something of value is at stake and where the outcome is uncertain. Risk results from the interaction of vulnerability, exposure, and hazard (Hagenlocher et al., 2018).

During this exercise, participants identify factors to characterize the exposure, the hazards, the vulnerability, and the socio-economic impacts on a specific topic. The results of the risk chain determine the rest of the adaptation pathways development exercise, since it is based on the risk identified collectively by the participants that the indicators, thresholds and then solutions are determined (sessions II and III).

To illustrate, we will use the example of the workshop conducted by the Westcountry Rivers Trust in the West Country Region, England.

Box 3.1: Example Session I in West Country Region, England

West Country Region held the first workshop online on the 18th of February 2022. Seven participants attended from different types of organisations: governmental bodies, NGOs, and the private sector.

The current and projected climate conditions identified are heavy rainfall events, floods, extended periods of dry weather, droughts, less difference between seasons, increased droughts, increased storms, rivers warming, ocean warming and acidification, and increased uncertainty around the Gulf Stream.

At the regional scale of the West Country Region, participants identified risk to health for older populations, danger to life from storms, wildfire on the moors, erosion, changing seasonal patterns, and impacts to crops. All participants agreed that the climate situation would worsen in the coming 10 years, so taking action to manage and to reduce risks and impacts is urgent.

Three risk chains were designed: one for agriculture, one for the water sector, and one for biodiversity. Here, we focus on the risk chain developed for the water sector because it is the most complete with quantified thresholds.

The risk chain for the water management sector was developed by two participants of the first workshop: a fishery owner and a member of staff from the Cornwall authorities. The risks to be addressed are the water quality failures, the weak water flows and the water shortage.

Figure 20 Example of a risk chain developed by the West Country Region on water management

3.1.2 Session II: Climate vulnerability, impacts and projections

During the second session, scientific information was brought in to support the work conducted in the first session. The goal is to substantiate these aspects with available scientific knowledge and information. The most prominent risks and risk levels for the region can be drawn scientifically. The next objective is to determine the risk impact and threshold values of identified climate change hazards. This is crucial to provide ground for a solid discussion and proposal of solutions.

Box 3.2: Example Session II in West Country Region, England

Risk levels were defined during the second workshop in the West Country Region, which took place online on the 3rd of March 2022. Seven people attended Workshop 2 from different types of organisations: governmental bodies, NGOs, and the private sector.

The work was done collectively, and participants identified the main concern of the sector in the first stage of the discussion. They agreed that the most prominent risk to be addressed in the water management sector is the degradation of water quality and the decrease in availability due to climate change.

Several indicators were proposed by participants to assess the water quality degradation: safety for recreation use, river flows, quality standards, mortality rates of fish and biodiversity, and eutrophication events in Summer. Meeting quality standards was identified as the key indicator.

The critical thresholds were defined as follows:

Moving from low to medium impact/risk:

- Phosphate levels > 40 ug/L (SAC threshold NE Camel)
- Water quantity daily mean flow (m³/s) river Camel at Dunmere below 0.7 m³/s for extended periods

Moving from medium to high impact/risk:

- Phosphate levels > 50 ug/L WFD threshold
- Water quantity daily mean flow (m³/s) river Camel at Dunmere below 0.5 m³/s for extended periods

Moving from high to very high impact/risk:

- Phosphate levels > 70 ug/L elevated
- Water quantity daily mean flow (m³/s) river Camel at Dunmere below 0.4 m³/s for extended periods

3.1.3 Session III: Visions, solutions, and way forward

The third session aims to explore the vision and adaptation pathways for the region, the different solutions and the way forward.

The participants should be given an overview of the concepts of transformative adaptation (see Figure 21), to understand the framework, which will enable them to complete the exercises and transform their practices, instead of finding coping solutions.

Figure 21 Transformational adaptation vs incremental adaptation strategies (from: Cools et al. (2025))

Once the vision is defined, the adaptive measures can be chosen from the [catalogue tool](#) (policy changes, awareness campaigns, engineered / technological solutions, nature-based solutions, etc.). The goal is to develop adaptation pathways map specific for a sector, laying out solutions to address the most prominent risk.

Box 3.3: Example Session III in West Country Region, England

Adaptation pathways were developed during the third workshop in the West Country Region online on the 16th of March 2022. 7 participants attended the workshop 3.

Participants identified actions that can lead to the desired adaptation outcomes for each impact/risk level. Then, they assessed each proposed solution if it is relevant or not according to some criteria (cost, impact of the solution to the environment, danger, etc.).

Some options identified by the participants to address the prominent risk are the improvement of the catchment management to improve water quality, developing sustainable drainage systems, rehabilitating wetlands, or relocating vulnerable / exposed populations.

Figure 22 Example of the different adaptation pathways developed for the water management sector in the West Country Region

3.1.4 Completion of the adaptation pathways and selection of the preferred pathways

After the session, internal work with all the demonstrators was necessary to harmonize and complete the adaptation pathways design, as demonstrators adapted the methodology to their needs. Then, a multi-criteria analysis (MCA) was completed to evaluate the most desirable pathway for each demonstrator. A non-exhaustive list of criteria was created based on their relevance regarding the objectives of the task within the TransformAr framework. The criteria are effectiveness, cost, environmental sustainability, co-benefits, social acceptability, and associated risks. For every criterion, a score from 1 (minimal) to 5 (maximum) is given until they reach a consensus, completed by a justification of the scoring.

The method adopted by the demonstrators was slightly different: one demonstrator used their tool, four conducted the scoring based on internal group discussions, and the last one adopted a more individualized approach by having each participant score the pathways independently.

The West Country Region example is presented in [Figure 23](#).

Box 3.4: Example Selection of Pathways in West Country Region, England

Concerning the **Water management sector**, three pathways were defined:

- **Policy & Governance Pathway** which consists of improving water regulation, decentralization, public ownership of water companies.
- **Landscape Interventions Pathway** which consists of developing sustainable drainage systems; installing water storage systems; soft defences (e.g. wetland rehabilitation/managed retreat); NFM (e.g., wetland creation; buffer peak management; increase storage capacity)
- **Management & Society Pathway** which consists of improving catchment management to improve water quality; improving land management skills; awareness-raising & education, and relocating vulnerable communities

The MCA method was applied by Westcountry Rivers Trust to identify the preferred pathway. **Landscape Interventions Pathway** was selected as the preferred pathway for the water management sector. It has scored most highly due to high effectiveness and feasibility with low costs and minimal associated risks.

Pathways name	Description of the Pathway		Effectiveness Rate the effectivity of the pathway and its component adaptation measures/actions in achieving its adaptation objectives. (1-ineffective; 2-not particularly effective; 3-moderately effective; 4-effective; 5-very effective)	Feasibility Rate the Feasibility of the pathway component adaptation measures/actions (1-unfeasible; 2-not really feasible; 3-moderately feasible; 4-feasible; 5-very feasible)	Flexibility Rate the flexibility of the pathway component adaptation measures/actions (1-unflexible; 2-not particularly flexible; 3-moderately flexible; 4-flexible; 5-very flexible)	Cost How costly is the pathway component adaptation measures/actions? (initial and long-term expenses) (1-Extremely expensive; 2-not particularly expensive; 3-moderately expensive; 4-inexpensive; 5-very inexpensive)	Co-benefits Rate the number and quality of co-benefits emerging from this pathway. (1-very low; 2-low; 3-moderate co-benefits; 4-high co-benefits; 5-with high co-benefits)	Social acceptability Rate the level of support and acceptance of the pathway and its component adaptation measures/actions among stakeholders (1-Very low social acceptability; 2-Low social acceptability; 3-Moderate social acceptability; 4-High social acceptability; 5-Very high social acceptability)	Associated risks Rate the riskiness of the pathway and its component adaptation measures/actions implementation. (1-very risky, 2-risky; 3-moderate risk, 4- safe; 5- very safe)	Result
Landscape Interventions	Develop sustainable drainage systems; installing water storage systems; soft defences (e.g. wetland rehabilitation/managed retreat); NFM (e.g. wetland creation; buffer peak management; increase storage capacity)	Score	5	4	5	3	5	3	3	4
		Explanation	Developing SuDS, water storage, soft defences and NFM are highly effective adaptation actions. They can be assessed & implemented on a case-by-case basis, meaning they can be adapted to suit local environmental pressures. Furthermore, studies show that "Nature-based solutions can help people adapt to the effects of change and disasters whilst slowing warming and protecting biodiversity, with many more positive consequences, fewer risks and lower costs than engineering-based approaches". 1	WRT have a strong regional reputation for our expertise in nature-based solutions for natural flood management, climate change mitigation & adaptation, phosphate mitigation, etc. Building on WRT's strong relationships with key regional actors (local authorities, charitable organisations, etc), delivering a greater abundance of landscape interventions is a highly feasible adaptation pathway. The only contingencies are funding and landowner participation, which seem surmountable given policy pressures are driving greater financial incentives for sustainable land use change.	NBS for climate change adaptation are highly flexible, as each intervention design is bespoke to the selected site.	Studies show that whilst 'engineered approaches have immediate, measurable impacts and are particularly effective in reducing the impacts of specific hazards over the short-term [...], they are expensive and deliver few if any co-benefits. In contrast, NBS is affordable, provides a wide range of ecosystem services and offers protection from multiple hazards, which is important as hazards seldom occur in isolation, but can take place simultaneously or in a cascade'. - 3	"Protecting and supporting biodiversity and ecosystems are fundamental to climate resilient development because of their crucial roles in adaptation and other services to communities. Nature-based solutions (NBS) for adaptation that are implemented with environmental and social protection and support measures can offer multiple benefits for biodiversity and society; they are a critical part of an overall integrated adaptation strategy." - 4	As "perspectives and values vary greatly both across and within the contexts of NBS sites", they "should be explored on a case-by-case basis but with systematic consideration of relevant variables". WRT works with landowners to implement NBS to address a variety of issues & provide multiple co-benefits. The social acceptability of NBS in the context of WRT's work is high. As NBS are often small-scale, they do not often present a challenge to broader public perception, however due to political uncertainty around credit formation & funding for NBS implementation, some landowners remain skeptical.	The assessment concluded that despite the shortcomings of NBS and in the face of uncertainty around both risks and effectiveness, NBS is a 'low risk' or 'no regret' option that provides more positive consequences than those that are engineering-based.	This pathway has scored most highly due to high effectiveness and feasibility with low costs and minimal associated risks. It is a logical choice for the Westcountry region.

Figure 23 Example of the scoring of the most preferred pathways along with the justification in the West Country Region for the pathway called “landscape interventions” for the water management sector

3.2 Adaptation planning

The goal of **adaptation planning** is to make targets and solutions more concrete by evaluating climate risk reduction and economic criteria. The workshop-based approach of the [Playbook](#) facilitated the creation of sector-specific pathways for transformative adaptation. Through co-creation workshops, stakeholders discussed and selected a series of actions tailored to each sector and specific thresholds that represent the impacts of climate change on the discussed sector. These actions were chosen to maximize the benefits of transformative adaptation. Once the actions are identified, a critical next step is the operationalization of these adaptation pathways. This involves conducting comprehensive studies to understand the necessary conditions and potential barriers to the implementation of the chosen actions within a specific context.

3.2.1 Toolkit for Adaptive Action Planning

To identify necessary conditions and potential barriers, ACTIERRA, one of TransformAr's consortium partners, created a detailed [toolkit](#) for transforming preferred adaptation pathways into actionable operational plans. A key objective of this guide is to align these actions with existing regional and national climate and energy policies. This alignment ensures that climate change adaptation is integrated into all current and future projects and investments, promoting a holistic approach to climate resilience.

The action plan must clearly define the combination of actions and their types, distinguishing between hard and soft measures, as well as short-term and long-term initiatives. Additionally, the plan must identify the enabling conditions necessary for successful implementation. These conditions include aspects of governance, financing, and capacity building.

A toolkit for adaptation action planning was written, with the primary objective of equipping demonstrators with a comprehensive guide to transforming the preferred adaptation pathways into detailed, operational action plans. This transformation process is essential for moving from strategic planning to practical implementation, facilitating adaptation measures to be effectively executed at the local level.

Workshops, gathering local stakeholders within the demonstrators, were organized to design detailed action plans for each key sector per demonstrator to operationalize the preferred adaptation pathway.

The workshop was divided into **3 sequences**:

- The **preferred pathway validation**
 - The **definition of transformative adaptation vision**. Stakeholders were asked to envision the future of their sector 30 years ahead, considering the implementation of adaptation measures.
 - The **adaptation action plan development**. Based on the preferred pathway, participants were invited to identify the type of solutions, action leader, partners, deadline, estimated cost, monitoring, relevant existing programs, policies, and strategies that are aligned with the action plan.
-

Box 3.5: Example of adaptation toolkit in the West Country Region, England

On the 14th of May 2024, the action plan development chart (see Figure 2, 3 and 4 in [deliverable 3.7](#)) was presented to the 12 participants of the workshop by the Westcountry Rivers Trust. The group worked in pairs/groups of three to complete the chart for their selected action. The participants identified different actions such as water management and sustainable drainage and storage, increasing water storage and retention, buffering rivers from agriculture and sustainable farming practices, increasing interception, infiltration and retention, and sustainable road drainage.

For each of these actions, the participants provided (i) the timeframe (short term (1-2 years); medium term (5 years); long term (10 years/more)), (ii) the stakeholders involved (including public/private actors and NGOs), (iii) the monitoring indicators, (iv) the key enablers (funding programmes and relevant existing support) and (v) existing programmes/strategies.

3.2.2 Lessons learned about the action plan development

The demonstrators highlighted the following lessons learned and best practices:

- As for the development of adaptation pathways, it is important to avoid over-solicitation of stakeholders and to clarify the objectives and steps of the collaborative work.
- At the same time, it is essential to identify the relevant stakeholders to participate in this kind of exercise, which is more strategic.
- Time management is important, and time optimisation is required. Some information can be pre-filled before having the workshop with stakeholders.
- Tangible actions are required while defining such an action plan.
- The action plans were developed in the framework of a project.
- Participants raised questions about the financial sustainability of the work and the next steps for implementing the action plans.

Box 3.6: Specific lessons learned in the case of West Country Region, England

- It was suggested to organize the workshop entirely online rather than in a hybrid format to ensure better participation and coordination.
- Selecting an appropriate time of year is important to maximize participants' availability and engagement
- The integration of this process should align with broader territorial strategies to enhance its impact and coherence.
- There is a preference for developing a territorial action plan that addresses cross-cutting issues, rather than focusing solely on sector-specific actions.

4.0 Step 4: Assessing and selecting adaptation options

The main goal of **S4: Assessing and selecting adaptation options** is to facilitate a combination of solutions that maximizes expected impacts and benefits. To that aim, this section describes various ex-ante assessments on public acceptance, climate change damages, avoided damages, socio-economic impacts, sustainability, costs, and benefits, developed and conducted throughout the TransformAr project.

4.1 Public acceptance

To implement and upscale adaptation solutions, public support is crucial. Resistance could delay implementation, increase costs, ignore the needs of certain groups, and erode trust. Moreover, gauging how much the public would be willing to pay (e.g., in the form of taxes) is useful for financing purposes. TransformAr assessed the acceptance of climate adaptation solutions using Discrete Choice Experiments (DCEs) based on two surveys, a local one about stormwater management among 2000 residents in Lappeenranta and Gjøvik (Haoran et al., 2025), and a Europe-wide one on adaptation in general, among 9.072 households in Norway, Finland, the UK, Italy, Spain, and Greece ([Deliverable 6.1](#)).

Key concepts

Public support/ acceptance = The endorsement or approval of an idea or policy by citizens.

Willingness-to-pay (WTP) = The maximum amount a person is willing to pay for an adaptation solution. A way to assess public support.

Discrete Choice Experiment = A research method to understand preferences by asking individuals to make trade-offs between different options with varying attributes.

A common way to analyze the public's preferences is a discrete choice experiment. In such an experiment, participants fill out a survey in which they must choose their preferred options based on various hypothetical trade-offs in terms of attributes and costs, in this case, different kinds of adaptation solutions. Through the choices we can measure how much the public would be willing to pay for specific types of solutions, and what solutions are preferred over others.

DCE is a **Stated Preference method**, widely used in the environmental economics literature for non-market goods evaluation. Stated preference methods have an edge over revealed preference methods (where actual behaviour is observed) when testing out new ideas and policies that do not exist yet, and, therefore, for which revealed preference data are not available (Haab et al., 2020; Johnston et al., 2017). Environmental goods typically do not have a market, so assigning them a meaningful economic value cannot rely directly on market prices. As there are no directly observable market data, these studies resort to surveys to elicit people's preferences and attitudes towards the nonmarket good under scrutiny among the relevant population. They can also elicit people's attitudes towards preserving or improving these goods, that is, they can also cover attitudes towards policy actions. When conducting DCEs, one should be wary of hypothetical bias, which refers to individuals reporting unrealistic choices, behaviours, or values within surveys or experimental studies, in the sense that what respondents state that they would do hypothetically may differ from what they would do in real life (Buckell et al., 2020). For instance, ex-ante, the survey should be as realistic as possible and feel consequential to the respondent in terms of choices. Ex-post approaches include screening data for implausible responses based on responses or post-experimental questions (Colombo et al., 2022).

Box 4.1: European-wide Discrete Choice Experiment of adaptation solutions

Preferences and acceptance of adaptation solutions were assessed among 9.072 citizens, representative of the populations from almost all countries in which TransformAr’s adaptation solutions were implemented (Greece, Italy, Spain, Finland, Norway, and the United Kingdom).

Questionnaire and data collection. Each participant is presented with seven choices between adaptation solutions (also called ‘choice cards’), comparing no policy/no tax to a specific policy package and tax. The policy packages varied in the following attributes: sector(s) covered by the policy (water supply, surface waters, coastal areas, agriculture, forests, fisheries or a combination), the type of measures (infrastructure, regulation, nature-based, or a combination), and cost to the tax payer (from 100 to 1500 extra income tax per year for the next 10 years). An example choice card is shown in Figure 24.

	Program D <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO Program D <input type="checkbox"/>
Water supply for drinking and all other residential, commercial, and industrial uses		The program would not be implemented, its benefits would not be experienced, and you and everyone else would pay nothing.
Surface waters (rivers, lakes, lagoons)		
Coastal areas	Covered	
Agriculture	Covered	
Forests		
Fisheries and aquaculture		
Type of measure	infrastructure	
Geographical coverage: percent of national territory	60%	
Climate change damages reduction (percent)	50%	
Cost to each taxpayer	£110 each year for the next 10 years	
	<input checked="" type="radio"/> in favour of program D	<input type="radio"/> against program D

Figure 24 Example of choice card in the discrete choice experiment.

Data analysis and results. Econometric models were used to determine which attributes are important and how much the participants were willing to pay for different types of solutions. Results were compared between countries. Overall, the participants were accepting of and willing to pay for adaptation solutions. Comparing sectors, respondents place the highest value on policies for water supply, followed by surface waters, forests, agriculture, coastal areas and fisheries. In terms of policy types, there was a slight preference towards infrastructure policies, but no clear preference among the other types. The overall willingness-to-pay for a policy package covering all sectors and solution types is 1346 euros per year. Participants with a higher salary and those with a university degree were willing to pay slightly more.

Comparing countries, Italy and the UK place the highest value on protecting coastlines and agriculture compared to other countries. While in all countries fisheries were least valued, Italy and the UK also find fisheries more important than other countries. Spain stands out in the higher value they place on the full policy package, water supply, agriculture, and forests compared to other countries. Overall, UK citizens place a lower value on adaptation solutions than the other countries in the study.

Box 4.2: Local DCE of private Stormwater Management solutions in Lappeenranta (Finland) and Gjøvik (Norway)

For the local study, results indicate that residents prioritise stormwater management (SWM) measures that reduce property damage and water runoff while decreasing water pollution. The interest in SWM measures that improve the aesthetics of their property and community was relatively lower. In both locations, residents are averse to SWM requiring frequent maintenance. However, there is a significant diversity in preferences, as the relative importance of factors varies widely among respondents, especially for maintenance frequency and aesthetic improvement. Respondents in Lappeenranta are prepared to invest up to €4,820 per household for a one-time installation investment if it effectively reduces the risk of property damage. This is 36% more than double the amount that people in Gjøvik are prepared to spend for the same purpose (€2,130) and suggests prioritising strategies to mitigate property damage risks in Finland.

Figure 25 Examples of SWM measures presented to the respondents.

Gjøvik respondents prioritise runoff reduction, showing a WTP of up to €3,550 per household, indicating that runoff reduction (and improving water quality) should be a key focus for SWM improvement in this city. Runoff reduction is also highly valued in Lappeenranta, but with a WTP of €3,736, residents there show a higher interest in a moderate effort in runoff reduction (50%) rather than going for a 75% reduction, for which they are willing to spend €550 less. Additionally, respondents showed positive preferences and WTP for aesthetic improvements, which the local government can leverage as motivational factors to engage citizens in SWM initiatives. It is crucial that both governments and citizens act together to address climate challenges, and our results are encouraging as they indicate strong citizen willingness to contribute, for instance, to a stormwater fee.

The study finds that respondents' preference for SWM is influenced by factors including age, income, education, whether they had experienced floods, water quality in the local community, and the market value of the property. Although older generations and low-income residents may show less interest in

SWM improvements and related financial investments, governments should ensure equitable distribution of strategies across all income levels. Residents with higher-value properties tend to show greater preference for SWM investments, suggesting the need for targeted approaches like providing subsidies to lower-income residents, conducting education campaigns about SWM benefits, and leveraging technology for monitoring system maintenance. These strategies can help create more inclusive and comprehensive SWM that address the varied needs of different community segments.

The findings suggest a promising level of citizen engagement in SWM, with the potential for even greater investment in SWM strategies across the region.

The two studies on public acceptance conducted within TransformAr show that adaptation solutions stand a good chance of being warmly welcomed in Europe, but those dealing with water resources are likely to meet the highest interest, and those dealing with fisheries are likely to trigger much less support within the public. The results reinforce a key intuition around which our project has been designed and developed: water is a fundamental need and a top priority for European households. They are concerned about climate change impacts and value concrete actions to curb them, and the concern over future availability of water triggers the highest willingness to pay for adaptation measures. Certain private measures, especially those that require more maintenance, may need more support from policymakers, such as innovative incentives like tax breaks, subsidies or maintenance support for property owners (Brown et al., 2016; Green et al., 2012). Additionally, educational campaigns can enhance understanding and engagement among homeowners (Lieberherr and Green, 2018). Future implementers and researchers can test public acceptance for other types of public adaptation solutions or incentives for less popular private solutions.

4.2 Avoided damages and benefits per demonstrator

During the TransformAr project, National Center for Research Demokritos (NCSR) developed a [framework](#) to assess **climate change damages** (unmitigated adverse impacts) and **avoided damages** (benefits from effective mitigation/adaptation). The approach quantifies avoided damages by comparing a baseline scenario (current or projected climate impacts) against outcomes after implementing solutions, with two methodologies tailored to data availability:

1. High Data Availability: KPI-Based Approach

- a. **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)** are grouped into five impact categories: Physical, Economic, Environmental, Health and Social.
- b. KPIs are selected to directly or indirectly represent the damages and effectiveness of a solution.
- c. It is essential that it can be quantified based on regional relevance, solutions, and data accessibility.
- d. Damages (values of KPIs) are categorized as:
 - **Direct** (physical impacts)
 - **Indirect** (economic/environmental ripple effects)
 - **People-related** (health/social costs)
- e. Data sources include modelling data (e.g., results from WP2, downscaling methods or statistical approaches to extrapolate or project), IoT sensors, regional datasets, and expert estimates.

2. Sparse Data: High-Level Approach

- a. Based on the **IPCC risk formula**: $Risk = Hazard \times Exposure \times Vulnerability$.
- b. **Damage estimation** uses three formulas:
 - **Direct damages**: Combines event frequency, intensity, and risk indices, informed by recent climate econometrics (e.g., global temperature shocks' systemic impacts).
 - **Indirect damages**: Accounts for 40% of direct damages (fixed factor) plus systemic economic disruptions, though simplified assumptions may overlook sectoral complexities.
 - **People damages**: Estimates health/social costs per capita but may underrepresent non-health impacts (e.g., displacement, mental health).
- c. Limitations include reliance on fixed coefficients (e.g., 40% indirect damage) and delayed climate effects.
- d. **Damage Reduction & Efficiency Factors**
- e. **Efficiency factors** (aligned with Green Climate Fund criteria) measure how solutions reduce damages. These are derived from pre/post-implementation data or expert judgment.
- f. Emphasizes **paradigm shifts** toward resilience and low-carbon development.

Avoided damages assessment

After choosing the way to estimate damages; either (i) High data availability or (ii) sparse data availability approach, the avoided damages assessment is performed in comparison between two states.

- a. Baseline (Bs): Represents the current situation with current climate condition.
- b. Climate Change (CC): Represents the future following a climate scenario.

The states are assessed for two cases in the Baseline scenario and one for the Climate Change scenario:

- i. No Solution implementation (nS): It is assessed for the Baseline scenario as representation of the current situation (ground truth) and the climate future scenarios
- ii. Solution implementation (S): It is assessed for the Baseline Climate Change scenarios and defines the score of the solution in different context.

Depending on what avoided damaged the end-user wants to estimate the two stages can be estimated

- A. Short-term: It describes the immediate avoided damages the end-user has, in the current climate conditions by implementing adaptation measures.
- B. Long-term: It describes the avoided damages the end-user has for future climate conditions by implementing adaptation measures now.

The difference between the damages of the two states for either short-term or long-term, represents what can be avoided, hence, the avoided damages. This framework enables policymakers and practitioners to quantify avoided damages, guiding targeted climate adaptation strategies.

Box 4.3: Example of Avoided Damages assessment in Municipality of Egaleo (MOE), Greece

Step 1. Identify the Climate Avoided Damages team support by local stakeholders and experts: An effective Avoided Damages framework requires an interdisciplinary team with extensive knowledge and experience in various sectors, alongside various levels of governance and supporting organizations. The team requires (1) a project lead who can manage the entire process and ensure the assessment and results are correct and (2) specialized experts in the fields of climate change adaptation/mitigation. Also, societal experts and urban planners should be invited if needed. In the case of Egaleo this was covered by actors from MOE, NCSR, and expertise of other TransformAr partners.

Step 2. Plan the Avoided Damages Plan: Once the team was assembled, the NCSR team led the development of a project plan that outlines how the Avoided Damages assessment will be conducted based on MOE solution implementation and gathering of preliminary data and information.

Step 3. Define the climate hazard: In general, this step involves the identification of the (climate-related) stressors and parameters that influence the area of interest. In the case of MOE, the main focus was on heatwaves with the data coming from NCSR specialized climate simulations.

Step 4. Determine the most impactful solutions (KPIs): This step builds on the list of solutions and provides a way to identify the effectiveness of the solutions. In the case of MOE, the teams of experts with the support of NCSR identified the most suitable and quantifiable KPIs.

Step 5. Assess the damages from climate change: This step applies the damages assessment for the current climate conditions (Bs) and for the future climate scenario(s) (CC). The team followed the TransformAr's avoided damages framework and provided values for the chosen KPIs to assess the direct, indirect, and people damages for each hazard, without (nS) and with solution (S) implementation.

4.3 Transformational Adaptation Scorecard

The [TransformAr Scorecard](#) developed by UA is a self-assessment tool for developers or stakeholders of adaptation programs or projects to assess to what extent their project is transformational, along five principles: scope, impact areas, depth, temporality, and inclusivity. The goal is to identify whether certain principles can still be improved to create more long-term, systemic and impactful (transformational) change. The principles and the corresponding criteria were derived from a literature review on transformational adaptation (e.g., Chhetri et al., 2019; Deubelli and Mechler, 2021; Fedele et al., 2019; Kasdan et al., 2021; Scolobig et al., 2023). The criteria were translated into statements, easily answerable by project stakeholders. A schematic overview of the principles, criteria and indicators (statements) is presented in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Overview of TransformAr Scorecard criteria and indicators

Respondents are asked to reply to the statements with their level of agreement, from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. Based on the respondents' answers, scores are calculated for each criterion (see examples in Box 4.2). The results dashboard, at the end of the survey, then highlights whether the adaptation project scores poorly or highly on these criteria. This allows respondents to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their adaptation project from a transformational adaptation point of view. For example, if a project scores poorly on the criterion 'equitable', then project developers know that they should improve the consideration or involvement of vulnerable citizens (e.g., elderly, economically disadvantaged citizens). If a project scores highly on the criterion 'scalability', the project developers know that their efforts to make the project replicable contribute to the project's transformational character.

The assessment can be done before, during, or after implementing an adaptation project, but is ideally done ex ante, when improvements can still be made.

Box 4.4: TransformAr Scorecard applied to the Gjøvik demonstrator

Through an interview with the Municipality of Gjøvik, the University of Antwerp (UA) researchers obtained the following results dashboard for the Gjøvik demonstrator (the Citizen App for reporting flooding events to the municipality and the stormwater monitoring solution). As can be seen from these results, the solutions have low scores for multi-scale, governance, path-shifting, equitable, synergetic, and SDG-aligned. The low score for governance, for example, is due to a lack of stakeholder involvement in the decision-making processes. Transformational adaptation requires co-production with different levels of government, citizens, and stakeholder groups. The solution scores poorly on SDG-aligned because, although water quality is monitored, it does nothing to improve water quality and, therefore does not contribute to any additional environmental goals such as biodiversity on land and in water. The project scores highly on ‘systemwide’ because it applies to all citizens of Gjøvik, rather than just a few. It scores well on ‘restructuring’ because it changes the processes related to stormwater management (e.g., rather than driving around the municipality looking for households suffering from floods, the municipality now provides aid when alerted through the Citizen App). The project scores well on all temporality criteria because it considers future climate changes and can adapt to these changes flexibly, while also ensuring that future funding is available to guarantee its maintenance and use in the future. Hence, the results show that the demonstrator can be considered transformational for some criteria, while being rather incremental for others.

Figure 27 Example results from the Scorecard tool.

4.4 Ex-ante impact assessment

At the stage of deciding which solutions to implement, it is useful for decision-makers (e.g., a municipality) to know whether implementing the designed solution will be beneficial in terms of economic, social, and environmental impacts. However, assessing these impacts is challenging due to the diverse number of strategies, the dynamic nature of ecosystems, the unpredictability of climate-induced changes, the difficulty of evaluating social or cultural dimensions (e.g., aesthetic appreciation), and the limited time and resources of (local) authorities (Van Oijstaeijen et al., 2020).

Several tools to evaluate adaptation solutions exist. Van Oijstaeijen et al. (2020) provide an overview and evaluation. Most tools focus on biophysical features and do not incorporate economic considerations. This leads to struggles for (local) authorities to implement high-level policy goals. The results of this review fed a novel tool, developed in the Interreg-2seas Nature Smart Cities project: [The Nature Smart Cities Business Model](#) (NSC-BM). NSC-BM is a comprehensive tool for estimating ecosystem services' valuation qualitatively, quantitatively, and monetarily, overcoming the previously mentioned shortcomings of other tools. The tool is designed for green urban infrastructure, and in TransformAr replicated for the urban nature-based solutions that are currently implemented. The tool can be applied to any potential solution that involves changing urban or natural infrastructure. The main goal of the tool is to compare a new scenario (the potential or implemented solution) to a baseline scenario (the same area before implementation in terms of social, monetary, and environmental costs and benefits). The Excel-based model template and instructions are freely accessible on the NSC-BM [webpage](#).

Ideally, the assessment is conducted by a team of decision-makers and technical project staff (e.g., within a municipality) who can gather at least the following information: spatial structure per landscape element (e.g., lawn, trees, grey infrastructure) in m² of both the old and new scenario, a selection of which ecosystem services are prioritized (e.g., food, carbon sequestration, water retention, ...), number of households and persons within a 100-meter radius of the project, average amount of annual rainfall in the municipality, and cost indications in unit values per m² (both investment and maintenance for the new scenario, and maintenance costs for the old scenario). Box 4.5 presents the model's steps.

Box 4.5: Steps of the Nature Smart Cities – Business Model

- 1. Project description:** The project site before and after renewal is defined in terms of land cover types (e.g., grass, grey infrastructure, ...).
- 2. Selection of Ecosystem Services:** Users indicate which ecosystem services matter for the project, usually determined by the local authorities (e.g., water retention or biodiversity).
- 3. Parameter selection:** Depending on the selected Ecosystem Services, additional parameters should be filled out (e.g., Average precipitation per year).
- 4. Quantification:** The model quantifies relevant outcomes, comparing the old and new scenarios (e.g., in terms of m³ water retained).
- 5. Qualification:** Users score the different scenarios in terms of contribution to each of the ecosystem services from 0 (no contribution) to 3 (excellent contribution).
- 6. Monetization:** The model uses pre-programmed costs and benefits, which can be adjusted to more accurate values by the user, to calculate the costs and benefits of the scenarios.
- 7. Factsheet:** The tool generated a factsheet of the results.

In the TransformAr project, this model was applied to various cases, among which a solution in Lappeenranta, Finland, as presented in Box 4.6. A written report of the analysis can be found in [D3.6](#).

Box 4.6: Applying the NSC-BM to a case in Lappeenranta, Finland

The case under study is located in the city of Lappeenranta, Finland, and covers 1750m² of residential area in Koulukatu Street. The area is at risk of water stress and flooding. Therefore, 245m² of the area is transformed into an infiltration area. In the NSC-BM, we compare the old area to the new area in terms of landscape types and ecosystem service outcomes.

Figure 28 The case and location of Lappeenranta, Finland.

The baseline scenario (old street) consisted mostly of grey infrastructure and some lawn and trees. The new scenario includes a larger variety of greenery (grass, flowers, shrubbery) and an infiltration area. The municipality determined that **water retention and infiltration, habitat for biodiversity, aesthetic appreciation, carbon sequestration** and **air filtering** are the prioritized ecosystem services.

After filling out the important ecosystem services and requested parameters, the model quantifies contributions to ecosystem services (see Figure 29). The largest impact is on **water retention**; the new scenario retains 867 m³ water per year compared to 273 m³ in the previous scenario. The new street also **sequesters** more **carbon** than the old (108 kg/year compared to 97 kg/year). **Air filtering** is also improved (6,27 rather than 5,56 kg/ year). Finally, the new scenario is a better **habitat for biodiversity**, with increased potential for birds, butterflies and bees. Qualitatively, the new scenario also consistently scored higher than the old scenario (baseline).

The NSC-BM is a tool that is **easily understood** by many, facilitates **effective communication** among stakeholders, and provides **valuable insights** into cost implications. The NSC-BM can be completed in a few hours to a few days, depending on how much of the data requirements are readily available. It is a rapid assessment to gather first insights into the costs and benefits of a potential investment in urban nature-based solutions. The results can also be used in further cost-benefit analyses or the stipulation of **adaptation pathways**. The tool also has some limitations. The pre-programmed ecosystem impacts, costs, and benefits allow for rapid assessment, but may not be accurate in every situation. The values in the model are set for the case study cities in the Nature Smart Cities project (e.g., Belgium, the Netherlands, ...). Finland has higher prices, and while adjustments have been made towards Finnish prices, the values are likely underestimated. The tool allows for updating the pre-programmed values to local values.

The estimated values are intended to compare scenarios (rather than to calculate absolutes on the monetary value of ecosystem services). The rapid assessment of costs and benefits of specific, nature-based solutions provides initial numbers that can be put forward for **decision-making** at an early level. The outcome can reveal whether the estimated costs and benefits align with the expectations and whether specific weaknesses need to be mitigated.

4.5 Sustainability assessment of transformational pathways

The Sustainability Rating Methodology (SRM), developed by LUT University, provides a holistic framework for evaluating the environmental, economic, and social sustainability of tested and validated solutions. As the demand for effective sustainability assessments grows, SRM addresses this need by aligning with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) indicators, ensuring its relevance for stakeholders aiming to meet global sustainability targets. It integrates Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) and Handprint Thinking (HT), providing a structured and actionable assessment process.

The SRM methodology follows a four-phase approach: Scoping, Implementation, Data Process, and Assessment, which offers detailed guidance for conducting sustainability evaluations. By adapting to local conditions, the method can be applied across diverse contexts. This flexibility, combined with the integration of risk assessment, enables balanced decision-making by identifying both the potential benefits and challenges of each solution.

SRM is used to assess the sustainability of validated solutions and the region-specific portfolio (RSP) level across the six demonstrators: Lappeenranta (Finland), Westcountry Region (UK), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Guadeloupe (France), and Egaleo (Greece). A total of 19 tested solutions are evaluated, representing a wide range of nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing mechanisms, insurance models, and behavioural change solutions (see Table 1 in Section 0.0 Introduction for an overview of the solutions). Each solution's performance is assessed through both common and tailored performance categories, reflecting local contexts to ensure transparency and comparability.

Box 4.7: Application of Sustainability Rating Method in Lappeenranta, Finland

The sustainability profile of the region-specific portfolio (RSP) of Lappeenranta (Finland) includes four solutions: URB (nature-based urban stormwater solution), SWMM (stormwater monitoring), CAF (Citizen App Finland), and CEI (Choice Experiment survey). The data used in this assessment comes from a structured, multi-stage process beginning with systematic data gathering through participatory interviews and supported by diverse sources, such as monitoring reports, field studies, and institutional documentation. These sources include key project deliverables like regional solution portfolios and learning stories on various solution types. Quantitative data is collected via field and lab measurements, while qualitative data is validated through stakeholder inputs and supporting documentation. Scores are normalized and aligned with SDG sub-goals to ensure consistency, reliability, and a comprehensive sustainability evaluation of the adaptation solutions.

Figure 30 provides an overview of the sustainability profile. The RSP focuses on six primary targeted SDGs based on the objectives, with co-benefits extending to four other SDGs. The profile highlights the performance of each solution against these targets, where indicator values are converted to a 0 to 5 scale, with 0 representing no progress and 5 representing full achievement. The profiles also include an interpretation, highlighting successes, areas needing improvement, uncertainties, and actions for further development and next steps.

The sustainability profiles generated through SRM offer valuable insights for future adaptation and upscaling efforts. The methodology’s iterative development and testing in different regions contribute to refining sustainability metrics, improving the applicability of the SRM framework, and supporting evidence-based decision-making. These profiles will also aid in replicating successful solutions in other regions, further promoting the wider dissemination of transformational adaptation practices.

4.6 Demo-level modelling analysis focusing on water-energy- food nexus

With the energy sector being the largest cause of greenhouse gas emissions, it plays a central role in the adaptation and mitigation of climate change. However, energy is closely related to other sectors, one example being the water sector, where water is used in the energy supply processes (e.g. for cooling purposes), and conversely, energy is needed for the provision of (fresh) water, for example through pumping or desalination. To analyse these issues, an open-source energy modelling framework (The Global Energy System Model – [GENeSYS-MOD](#)) has been applied and expanded to cover the energy-water nexus as a whole. GENeSYS-MOD, as developed by Löffler et al. (2017), is a cost-optimizing linear program that aims to find the least-cost solutions for the development of the energy system towards the future. In doing so, it considers all energy sub-sectors, such as buildings, industry, transportation, electricity, and,

in the updated version, also water desalination as a fresh water source. GENeSYS-MOD takes into account data points and assumptions on future energy, mobility, and water demands, as well as technology data such as costs and efficiencies, plus resource potentials, like installable capacities of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems or available biomass resources. Also, political targets and frameworks, such as carbon limits or prices, renewable targets, or import restrictions, can be modeled and included in the scenario analysis. Figure 31 showcases the most relevant inputs and outputs of the GENeSYS-MOD framework. As part of the analyses for the demonstrators of the TransformAr, the model was applied to the case of Guadeloupe (Barani et al., 2025).

Figure 31 Most relevant inputs and outputs of the GENeSYS-MOD framework.

Box 4.8: Application of GENeSYS-MOD in Guadeloupe

The Guadeloupe archipelago, situated in the eastern Caribbean Sea with a population of approximately 400,000 inhabitants, faces distinctive challenges in realizing a sustainable and resilient energy transition owing to its nature - a distributed island system. These unique challenges include the absence of energy interconnections, limited domestic energy resources, substantial dependence on fossil fuels, and considerable load variance. These factors necessitate specialized attention in the analysis of the energy system transition, as it is envisioned in their current policy plans. In addition, Guadeloupe faces severe issues with its fresh water supply, with frequent cuts in supply as well as water pollution (e.g., from pesticides in the agricultural sector) being major issues (UNHR, 2024).

Therefore, current modelling tools had to be expanded to match the unique challenges of the demonstrator. Especially tourism and agriculture, two of the main cornerstones of Guadeloupe's economy, require large amounts of fresh water and rely on a consistent supply, driving the need for analyses of potential solutions in both the energy and water sectors. In the assessment, three scenarios were compared: (i) a baseline scenario, focusing on unconstrained growth and pure economic

optimization, (ii) an Independence 2040 scenario, looking into self-sufficiency and fulfilment ambitious climate targets by 2040, and (iii) Independence 2050, adopting similar general policies as Independence 2050, but with the target year of 2050 and a stronger openness to maintaining traditional technologies in Guadeloupe.

The main findings show that across all scenarios, renewable energy sources emerge as the cheapest option for electricity supply, even in the baseline case, while providing other benefits, such as lower emissions and local pollution. One other general trend is that of electrification of the other sectors, specifically also transport and industry, across all scenarios, which comes with a significant decrease in primary energy demand, as well as a reduced reliance on imported fossil energy carriers like coal, petroleum products. or natural gas.

The entire model including the data set used for the study are available online on [GitHub](#), which also includes the tools used to generate the renewable timeseries and potentials. The overall modelling framework GENE SYS-MOD is also [available online](#), including all input data, GAMS and Julia model versions, and tools for data generation and conversion. This means that all results from the TransformAr project can be replicated and used by external users from the academic society, interested stakeholders, or policymakers. Also, this allows for replication studies, as the overall model framework is generic and mostly data-driven. Given the proper input data research, similar studies can easily be performed for other demonstrators and regions. Weather- and geo-based data such as timeseries for capacity factors or usable surface area for PV and wind installations can be generated automatically with the provided scripts that make use of open data sets and packages such as the ERA5 climate data set or the Atlite package for calculating renewable power potentials and time series. An example output for such installation potentials can be found in Figure 32. General techno-economic data regarding technologies is provided via the GENE SYS-MOD.data repository, meaning that for creating a new regional application of GENE SYS-MOD, the main data points to add are demands and demand projections, regional disaggregation (including trade capacities and allowed trade connections), and policy targets (e.g., emission reduction goals). Several usability improvements and automations are currently in development to make use of the framework easier for non-experts, to further improve the accessibility and replicability of the case studies.

Figure 32 Usable surface area for utility-scale PV installations (left) and rooftop-based PV systems (right) in Guadeloupe as generated via the provided tools.

5.0 Step 5: Implementing adaptation policies and actions

In **S5: Implementing adaptation policies and actions**, the selected solutions are implemented and validated on a regional level. In TransformAr’s demonstrators, a total of 20 adaptation solutions (not considering the replicator Gjøvik (Norway), who implemented solutions similar to Lappeenranta (Finland)) and innovations were identified to drive rapid and far-reaching improvements in the resilience of the seven demonstrators, see also Table 1 in the Introduction section. This section describes those solutions and key learnings on their implementation, replication potential, and bankability. The solutions, implemented in the demonstrators over the past three years, are categorized into five key themes:

Figure 33 The five types of adaptation solutions.

Building on Figure 33, specific solutions within these 5 themes include:

- **AWARENESS-RAISING AND BEHAVIOURAL CHANGE SOLUTIONS** - nudging experiments; citizens’ app for crowd sensing and real-time monitoring of extreme flooding events due to climate change events by citizens.
- **GOVERNANCE SOLUTIONS** - resilience index; coastal contracts for actors involved in coastal wetlands management; climate innovation hub.
- **NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS** - integrated constructed wetlands; nature-based solutions for urban stormwater management (e.g., greenery; green roofs); smart grids for coastal management.
- **TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS** - low-cost sensors; digital monitoring of flow rates and water quality; smart climate stations; real-time monitoring (intertidal monitoring; mussel raft monitoring); stormwater management systems.
- **FINANCING AND INSURANCE MECHANISMS** – payments for ecosystem services; adaptation fund; insurance mechanisms – damage functions as part of climate proofing; choice experiment for investors.

In September 2024, as part of WP4, five learning stories were developed, outlining the design and implementation of each experiment. An assessment of the solutions’ replicability potential was conducted in April 2025 as part of the same work package, resulting in the launch of a tool that enables territories to assess whether a solution is relevant and replicable within their own context.

5.1 Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions

Four awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions have been implemented across three TransformAr demonstrators to foster climate awareness, sustainable practices, and community resilience, each targeting specific groups with tailored strategies. The four solutions are:

- An **awareness-raising program (AWAR)** in the Municipality of Egaleo targeting 16-18-year-old children to make them more aware of climate change and its impact on the environment.

Figure 34 Awareness-raising class in Egaleo.

- A **Citizen app (CAE)** in the Municipality of Egaleo that displays data from weather stations in the region to create awareness.

Figure 35 Citizen app in Egaleo, Greece.

- A **Citizen app (CAF)** in Lappeenranta that displays stormwater information (also used in replicator Gjøvik, Norway).

Figure 36 Citizen app in Lappeenranta, Finland.

- A **nudging experiment (NUDG)** in Guadeloupe that nudges tourists on the archipelago to reduce their water consumption overall, but with more focus on water consumption in the shower.

Figure 37 Stickers and sensors from the nudging experiment in Guadeloupe, France.

Two years into the implementation of the solutions, preliminary insights reveal both promising outcomes and challenges, as highlighted in the [learning story on behavioural change solutions](#). In Egaleo, the awareness-raising program targeting students aims to build long-term climate resilience by educating youth, while the citizen app enhances communication between the public and the municipality, fostering better climate engagement. Similarly, in Lappeenranta, CAF is boosting community involvement in local climate initiatives, encouraging feedback and collaboration with city authorities. In Guadeloupe, NUDG showed initial success in reducing shower times and increasing ecological awareness, despite operational challenges in the installation and synchronization of sensors. These early findings demonstrate alignment with the projects' goals of increasing climate awareness, fostering community engagement, and encouraging sustainable behaviours, setting a strong foundation for future efforts.

Building on these preliminary lessons from the implementation phase, the **evaluation of the solutions' replicability potential** has begun. Interviews were conducted with representatives from the different demonstrators to identify key criteria for successfully replicating these solutions in other territories. For example, in Guadeloupe, the success of the nudging experiment relies on the presence of a dedicated team on the ground to support implementation and engagement efforts. Additionally, the level of awareness among hotels regarding water availability challenges and climate change adaptation plays a key role in the effectiveness and replicability of the solution. In Egaleo, long-term commitment to climate education and collaboration between schools and local authorities were identified as essential factors for the success of the awareness-raising program.

By evaluating how these key criteria align with their local context, territories seeking to replicate a solution can better assess its feasibility, potential challenges, and necessary adaptations. This approach will enable them to determine whether the solution can be effectively implemented and sustained within their specific conditions, ensuring a higher likelihood of success.

5.2 Governance schemes

Three governance solutions have been implemented across three TransformAr demonstrators to overcome challenges in adapting to the consequences of climate change. These governance challenges relate to issues such as shifting political priorities, conflicting interests, and limited opportunities for change. Three examples of governance solutions are:

- A **Resilience Index (RI)** in Galicia providing a comprehensive assessment of climate adaptation needs for the mussel aquaculture sector.
- A **coastal contract (COAST)** in Oristano to manage coastal wetlands more effectively by overcoming the fragmentation of local governance through collaborative decision-making and centralized climate data monitoring.

Figure 38 Meeting of Coastal Contract Coordination Group in Oristano, Italy.

- A **Climate Innovation Hub (CIH)** in Egaleo, a physical space in the city that facilitates the sharing of climate and weather data with policymakers and citizens.

The implementation of governance solutions across TransformAr demonstrators highlights key lessons for overcoming climate adaptation challenges. **Collaboration and stakeholder engagement** emerged as crucial success factors, with multi-actor cooperation proving essential in addressing fragmented governance and fostering shared commitment. For example, the **Coastal Contract in Sardinia** successfully brought together local authorities, civil society, and economic actors to create a shared action plan for wetland protection. **Data accessibility and informed decision-making** also played a critical role, as seen in the **RI in Galicia**, which provided decision-makers in the mussel aquaculture sector with actionable insights to guide climate adaptation policies. Additionally, **long-term sustainability depends on institutional support and local ownership**, ensuring that governance mechanisms remain effective beyond the project timeline. **CIH in Egaleo** further demonstrates how creating accessible spaces for public engagement and innovation can drive ongoing climate resilience efforts. These findings underscore the need for integrated, adaptive, and participatory approaches to climate governance to drive meaningful and lasting change. The learning story on governance schemes can be downloaded [here](#).

As a result, several essential criteria have been identified for replicating these solutions. For instance, to implement a coastal contract, **the public sector must have the administrative capacity and experience** to navigate legal and regulatory frameworks, facilitating the coordination of the process and ensuring the drive for commitments. Furthermore, securing **multisector buy-in** and collaboration is crucial, as it fosters constructive dialogue and strong engagement.

5.3 Nature-based solutions

Three nature-based solutions (NBS) have been implemented across three TransformAr demonstrators to overcome challenges in adapting to the consequences of climate change. The project's goal is to accelerate and upscale the implementation of climate resilience solutions in different socio-ecological contexts by leveraging NBS. Among these solutions are:

- **Urban stormwater management (URB)** in Lappeenranta to address flood risks.

Figure 39 Biofiltration areas in Lappeenranta, Finland.

- A **Smart Gate system (SG)** in Oristano involving real-time monitoring and adaptive management of water levels in the wetlands.

Figure 40 Technical scheme of the Smart Gate system in Oristano, Italy.

- **NBS to address water pollution and habitat loss in agricultural landscapes (ICW)** in South West England, including riparian buffers and floodplain wetlands, citizen science initiatives and ecosystem services markets.

The implementation of NBS across TransformAr demonstrators highlights the potential for these approaches to address diverse climate challenges in different socio-ecological contexts. In Lappeenranta, the combination of biofiltration areas, real-time monitoring systems, and citizen engagement has proven effective in mitigating urban stormwater flooding, though challenges remain in data accuracy and private landowner involvement. In Oristano (Italy), the SG system for coastal and wetland management addresses environmental degradation and flood risks, but success depends on continuous stakeholder coordination and accurate data integration. Meanwhile, in the Westcountry Rivers Trust region of the UK, NBS such as riparian buffers and ecosystem services markets have been key in tackling diffuse water pollution and habitat loss, with stakeholder engagement and data management remaining key challenges. Across all cases, successful NBS implementation relies on collaboration, data integration, and stakeholder engagement, while scaling up these solutions requires addressing ongoing challenges in coordination, data accuracy, and financial mechanisms. The experiences across these regions provide valuable lessons for replicating NBS in other contexts, emphasizing the importance of **community involvement, adaptive management, and sustainable financial incentives** for long-term success.

The learning story on NBS (D4.3) can be downloaded [here](#).

5.4 Digital and technological solutions

The implementation of four digital and technological solutions across three TransformAr demonstrators has provided valuable insights into addressing climate adaptation challenges. Some of these solutions are:

- **Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)** in Galicia, which monitors sediment dynamics and environmental conditions in real time to predict risks and protect shellfish habitats.
- **Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM)** in Galicia, which uses IoT technology to provide real-time data on mussel health and environmental conditions, enabling farmers to adapt to changing conditions.

Figure 41 Mussel Raft Monitoring in Galicia, Spain.

- **Smart Climate Stations (SCS)** in Egaleo, designed to monitor local temperature variations and air quality, helping city planners develop targeted interventions.
- **Stormwater Management System (SWM)** in Lappeenranta, which tracks stormwater quality in real time, allowing the city to take prompt action when pollution levels increase.

The deployment of these solutions underscores the potential of digital technologies in improving climate resilience across diverse environments. In Galicia, both the **INTERM** and **MRM** systems demonstrated the importance of integrating local knowledge with digital tools, fostering collaboration between researchers and local stakeholders. Similarly, the **SCS** solution in Egaleo highlighted the value of granular, localized data in addressing urban heat island effects and enhancing the city's climate adaptation strategies. Meanwhile, Lappeenranta's **SWM** system exemplified the challenges of retrofitting existing infrastructure with new technologies, emphasizing the need for adaptable solutions based on local contexts.

The key lessons from these experiences demonstrate that successful digital solutions depend on active stakeholder engagement, real-time data accuracy, and the capacity to tailor technologies to the specific needs and challenges of each region. These solutions have the potential for wider replication and can be crucial for tackling similar climate-related issues in other areas.

The learning story on digital and technology solutions (D4.4) can be downloaded [here](#).

5.5 Insurance and financial solutions

Four financial solutions have been implemented across four TransformAr demonstrators to scale up climate adaptation financing and investments. These solutions address the need for innovative funding mechanisms and risk mitigation strategies. The relevant solutions are:

- A **Discrete Choice Experiment** (CEI) in Finland and Norway to assess citizens' willingness to invest in stormwater management.
- A **Payment for Ecosystem Services** (GB) scheme in the West Country Region, UK, through a nutrient credit trading platform.
- A **Local Adaptation Fund** (AF) in Guadeloupe to support climate adaptation projects.
- An **insurance scheme study** across all demonstrators to explore the role of insurance in addressing climate risks.

Key lessons learned from these solutions highlight the importance of innovative financial models. The Local Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe shows the potential of pooling local financial resources to implement climate adaptation projects, emphasizing the role of public-private partnerships in ensuring long-term sustainability. Similarly, the CEI in Finland and Norway provides valuable insights into citizens' willingness to invest in climate adaptation measures on their properties, helping tailor financial incentives and awareness programs to encourage action.

To ensure the replicability of these financial solutions, key factors must be in place. For the **Local Adaptation Fund** (AF), a diverse funding ecosystem involving public and private sectors, alongside strong local institutional support, is essential. This includes thorough feasibility studies and political backing to ensure the fund's longevity. In the case of the **Discrete Choice Experiment** (CEI), systematically gathering data and engaging citizens through tailored surveys is crucial for informing policy. Strong participation from local stakeholders, including urban planners and environmental experts, ensures the solutions are context-specific and actionable, facilitating adaptation at scale.

The learning story on financial solutions can be downloaded [here](#).

5.6 Replicability Assessment Tool

The [Replicability Assessment Tool](#), developed as part of WP4, provides a structured and quantitative approach to assess potential replicability in a given territory of the solutions developed in TransformAr. By evaluating potential replicators on the extent to which they meet key technical, financial, institutional, and environmental conditions required for replication, the tool enables decision-makers and project developers to identify the most viable solutions for replication. The tool integrates a set of defined conditions for replicability, defined with the demonstrators, and organized across twelve replicability categories (Table 5).

Table 5 Replicability Categories

Category	Description
Data & Analytics	This category determines whether a solution is replicable through the availability, quality, and utilization of data and analytics to support decision-making.
Environmental & Climatic	This category determines whether a solution is replicable considering environmental sustainability, climate resilience, and ecological impact.
Financial & Economic	This category assesses whether a solution is replicable from a financial and economic perspective, considering cost-effectiveness, funding sources, and financial sustainability.
Governance & Policy	This category evaluates the extent to which a solution is replicable within different governance structures and policy frameworks, ensuring regulatory alignment.
Monitoring & Evaluation	This category examines whether a solution is replicable by assessing its monitoring and evaluation frameworks, performance measurement, and impact assessment.
Operational	This category examines whether a solution is replicable based on its operational feasibility, efficiency, and ease of implementation across different contexts.
Planning & Risk Management	This category determines if a solution is replicable while managing risks effectively, including contingency planning, risk mitigation, and long-term resilience.
Political & Institutional Support	This category examines whether a solution is replicable given the level of political will, institutional support, and alignment with government priorities.
Scientific & Research Expertise	This category assesses whether a solution is replicable based on scientific validity, research backing, and the availability of expertise in the field.
Social & Behavioural	This category evaluates whether a solution is replicable considering cultural, behavioural, and societal factors that influence adoption and implementation.
Stakeholder & Community Engagement	This category evaluates the extent to which a solution is replicable through effective stakeholder involvement, community participation, and social acceptance.
Technical & Infrastructure Readiness	This category assesses whether a solution is replicable based on technological requirements, infrastructure availability, and technical feasibility.

To enhance precision, weightings were assigned to each condition based on the importance of that condition for the specific solution, in collaboration with the demonstrators through a co-constructive process. Drawing on their practical experience, demonstrators identified the key conditions that had influenced the experimentation of each solution in their local context. They were then invited to assess the relative importance of each condition — distinguishing those that were essential for successful replication from those that were desirable but less critical. This process ensured that the resulting weightings reflect grounded, context-sensitive judgements rather than theoretical assumptions.

The tool allows users to assess their alignment with these conditions by scoring themselves using a five-point Likert scale. The resulting scores are combined with condition weightings to produce a replicability score on a scale of 1 to 5, which reflects the overall potential for replicability of this solution within the given territory.

As an example, Table 6 presents the conditions influencing the replicability of the AF solution, grouped by thematic category. Each condition is described along with its weighting, which reflects the relative importance of that condition for successful replication of the AF in a new context. The user of the tool (i.e., the organisation or region interested in replicating the RI solution) can use this information to assess their own context: high-weighted conditions should be prioritised when assessing the areas for improvement and strengthening of the replicability.

Table 6 Example replicability conditions and weightings for the AF

Category	Replicability Condition	Description	Weighting
Financial & Economic	Financial Availability	There should be an availability and diversity of funds in the local ecosystem coming from various funding sources (e.g., international donors, national funds, private investors, etc.) that can be mobilised in an adaptation fund.	12%
	Openness to public-private partnerships	Openness to public-private partnerships is critical to encourage the establishment of partnerships and the integration of innovative financial engineering.	5%
Governance & Policy	Local Institutional Support	A strong local environmental agency or similar institution is needed to define and develop the fund's orientations according to the climate context of your region.	11%
Planning & Risk Management	Feasibility Study	A thorough feasibility study must be conducted to assess local financing needs and potential funding mechanisms.	11%
Political & Institutional Support	Political Backing	Strong political backing is necessary to ensure the fund's continuity and legitimacy.	13%
	Political Support	A meeting with relevant public authorities (e.g., State, Region, etc.) must take place to strategically orient the adaptation fund and bring together stakeholders in the territory.	11%
Scientific & Research Expertise	Organizational Capacity	There should be expertise and knowledge in climate change adaptation and financing to support project leaders with administrative and technical assistance, including structuring their projects.	12%
Stakeholder & Community Engagement	Communication & Outreach	There should be adequate communications, knowledge and expertise surrounding the fund, for example, to attract applicants and explain eligibility criteria.	13%
	Fostering participation of beneficiaries	Fostering participation and consultation with beneficiaries is essential to ensure that the Adaptation Fund meets real local needs.	12%

To support users in identifying focus areas for improvement, the tool identifies priority conditions and categories requiring further attention, which highlights performance at the category level. Additionally, conditions are classified by level of priority based on their weighting and user score. This classification supports users in identifying key focus areas and conditions where they can make the most room for improvement, given weightings and scores, to enhance replicability. Figure 42 presents the replicability results from a fictitious assessment of the replicability of the Adaptation Fund solution in a fictitious territory, with the legend for interpretation in Table 7.

Solution selected:		AF			
Category	Condition	Weighting	User Score	Weighted Score	Level of priority to maximise replication potential*
Stakeholder & Community Engagement	Communication & Outreach	13%	5	0,65	Low priority
Political & Institutional Support	Political Backing	13%	4	0,52	Low priority
Scientific & Research Expertise	Organizational Capacity	12%	3	0,36	High priority
Stakeholder & Community Engagement	Fostering participation of beneficiaries	12%	2	0,24	High priority
Financial & Economic	Financial Availability	12%	1	0,12	High priority
Governance & Policy	Local Institutional Support	11%	4	0,44	Low priority
Planning & Risk Management	Feasibility Study	11%	3	0,33	Low priority
Political & Institutional Support	Political Support	11%	2	0,22	Low priority
Financial & Economic	Openness to public-private partnerships	5%	5	0,25	Low priority
Replicability Score (out of 5):		3,13			

Figure 42 Replicability Assessment results for a hypothetical AF solution in a fictitious region.

Table 7 Interpretation of replicability

5	Highly replicable – the solution is fully replicable in your region / context with no significant barriers
4	Easily replicable – the solution is straightforward to replicate and will require minimal improvements in the scoring against replicability conditions
3	Moderately replicable – the solution can be replicated, but requires some improvements in the scoring against replicability conditions
2	Difficult to replicate – the solution can be replicated, but it would require significant effort to improve your scoring against the relevant conditions
1	Not replicable – the conditions required to replicate this solution are not met in your region / context and you would therefore struggle to replicate it without significant effort

Finally, a bubble chart is presented that illustrates the conditions by plotting user scores against weightings, with bubble size representing the corresponding weighted score (Figure 43). Users will find that larger bubbles highlight conditions with a greater influence on the overall replicability score. Particular attention should be given to large bubbles positioned in the lower-right quadrant, as these represent conditions that are both highly weighted and underperforming, indicating key areas for improvement. Conversely, conditions in the upper-right quadrant are both highly weighted and well-aligned with replicability criteria. To support visual identification, high-priority conditions are shown in green, while low-priority conditions are shown in yellow.

Figure 43 Bubble chart of Replicability Assessment Tool results (fictitious AF solution).

The Replicability Assessment Tool offers a structured approach to assessing the feasibility of replicating TransformAr solutions or similar climate adaptation initiatives, supporting decision-makers in enhancing replicability outcomes.

In conclusion, TransformAr’s experimental implementation of 20 adaptation solutions across six demonstrators has provided invaluable insights into addressing climate change impacts through diverse approaches. These solutions have demonstrated both the challenges and successes of adapting to climate change in various contexts. By providing a tool to evaluate the replicability of these solutions, TransformAr has paved the way for tailored, context-specific adaptations that can be scaled and implemented in other regions facing similar challenges. The lessons learned emphasize the need for comprehensive, inclusive, and adaptable strategies that ensure long-term sustainability and the successful integration of climate adaptation measures into diverse socio-environmental settings.

5.7 Financing and investment

5.7.1 Bankability

Analysing the bankability of adaptation projects is important to secure the practical implementation and upscaling of solutions. This is done by introducing an economic way of thinking and a creative approach to developing business cases for spatial climate adaptation projects and nature-based solutions. The bankability reports of TransformAr serve as an inspiration for the demonstrators and other adaptation practitioners in Europe to think beyond the traditional public funding schemes of public budgeting and subsidies for transformative climate adaptation projects.

Firstly, 20 interviews with financial institutions worldwide were conducted, including (ethical) banks, investors, fund managers, equity firms, and federations. They were questioned about current practices in adaptation finance, challenges, and solutions to upscale investment potential ([D5.3](#)). Key challenges identified included an unclear revenue model, a lack of standardized metrics, and limited expertise. Among other solutions, financial institutions highlighted blended financing as a crucial tool for addressing adaptation investment risks. It reduces financial uncertainty by leveraging public and private capital to create risk-sharing mechanisms—helping distribute risks between public and private entities and making investments more attractive and viable. The report concludes with a list of recommendations under three themes: (1) policy-making actions, (2) knowledge solutions and tools, and (3) project recommendations.

“As a bank you have to make sure you are able to be repaid by the client. That's what it always comes down to. Therefore, guarantee systems are essential. This makes public Investment Companies and the InvestEU programs so successful. What those programs do, is make the collective, that is the society, “pay for it” if it ends badly. That is sharing a risk, so that it becomes a small risk for each individual.”

- Sustainability officer ethical bank

Secondly, we demonstrate how this theoretical knowledge has been applied across the six TransformAr demo sites by developing six “bankability reports” ([D5.4](#)). Supported by previous deliverables in TransformAr, we gained insight into adaptation pathways, solution providers, beneficiaries, and the costs and benefits of adaptation solutions in different demo regions. By matching this information with alternative financing and funding instruments, we created a financial model to upscale private and blended investment in climate adaptation in the demo regions. We adopt a common methodological framework (Figure 44) to set up 6 region-specific financial schemes:

1. Impact bonds for agriculture and tourism in Guadeloupe (France).
2. Carbon credits for financing nature-based solutions in the West Country Region (UK).
3. A Co-financing model for improving water quality in Lappeenranta (Finland).
4. Collaboration through coastal contracts in Oristano (Italy).
5. Payment for ecosystem data in Galicia (Spain).
6. Value capturing mechanisms to fund heat reduction measures in Egaleo (Greece).

Figure 44 Methodological framework for 6 region-specific financial models for adaptation.

The exercise of developing these financial models confirms some of the challenges identified by financial institutions in the D5.3 study, such as the lack of evidence on the monetary revenue potential of nature-based solutions and the importance of governance support. On the other hand, these region-specific financial models highlight that benefits can arise for a broad range of stakeholders, and thus the need for cooperation between public and private investors. This is illustrated in the demo-case of Lappeenranta (Figure 45), where we propose a co-financing scheme where public investments are partly repaid by a stormwater fee and tourist tax.

Figure 45 Retention and infiltration measures on both public and private land could improve water quality and climate resilience in Lappeenranta, Finland.

While these financial models are conceptual and need a detailed quantitative assessment before implementation can be considered, we hope to illustrate that creative financial schemes can make adaptation happen and that existing financing instruments are at hand. Interviews with local financial stakeholders and workshops are being conducted to gather feedback on the models, which will be reported upon in the Bankability Reports (D5.5; *not available yet*). The models can subsequently be re-evaluated in future projects with the aim of achieving financial independence for adaptation solutions and solution providers.

5.7.2 Accelerating investment and decision-making

Assessments of the bankability of climate adaptation projects highlighted multiple barriers to accelerating the availability of private finance for climate adaptation. Of these, many were nationally or internationally significant factors, requiring extensive regulatory, legislative, and socio-cultural change to be successfully overcome. For organisations with little influence over policymaking, options for accelerating the flow of private capital into climate adaptation projects are limited. Nonetheless, research undertaken through TransformAr highlights how certain approaches can help enhance the degree to which climate adaptation is integrated into regional decision-making processes. These key learnings emphasize that building successful partnerships and working relationships with relevant actors, sectors, and organisations is critical to accelerating investment. For this effort to deliver significant impact, there must also be a degree of strategic analysis to ensure effort is spent efficiently.

In TransformAr's Westcountry region (UK) demonstrator, a Systems Thinking approach was mobilized to map the organisational influence and potential of the Westcountry Rivers Trust (WRT). This led to broad strategic alignment with regional partners to accelerate climate adaptation into decision-making and investment frameworks within Devon and Cornwall.

Systems Thinking

Cultivating a strong understanding of key systems for climate adaptation investment is a helpful step to visualising organisational influence. The resulting [system map](#) outlines relationships between key actors, networks, and organisations involved in the establishment of climate adaptation finance in the Westcountry region (see also Figure 46). The map also shows whether relationships between groups and factors are defined by positive polarity (black, +), negative polarity (red, -), dependency (yellow), potential relationships (purple), and positive ultimate outcomes (gold, dashed). Areas of organisational influence are signified by the green and blue zones with accompanying highlighted text. The green zones signify areas where WRT's work is already closely aligned with, or supportive of, the relevant factors. Blue zones signify areas of emerging or developing influence in new areas. Understanding existing areas of influence and activity within the wider system provides clarity about further action that can be taken to accelerate investment.

Figure 46 Example of a system map in the Westcountry region, UK.

From such a system map, strong organisational influences and potential or emerging future operations that may be relevant can be identified. The examples of **strong organisational influence** in this map include:

- 1) WRT participation in publicly funded green finance projects through winning bids or operating as part of a wider partnership. This helps to overcome the barrier around ‘lack of pilot projects’ for Nature-based Solutions (NBS).
- 2) WRT regularly works with landowners to improve trust and provide extensive support and advice on participating in green finance projects. This helps to overcome the barrier around inconsistent value of ecosystem services for landowners, increasing the likelihood of participation and engagement over time.
- 3) Working with the private sector (utility companies, infrastructure providers, ...) to support climate adaptation projects (E.g., [Upstream Thinking](#)). This provides a simple, effective method for accelerating private sector funding for NBS.
- 4) Participation in practitioner groups, including farm clusters and catchment partnerships. WRT currently runs several catchment partnerships and contributes to others. WRT also runs farm cluster groups designed to facilitate peer-to-peer learning amongst the farming community. These professional networks support knowledge sharing and collective problem solving for natural capital schemes, helping to overcome barriers around novelty and a lack of sufficient information for investors.

- 5) WRT has a strong track record of developing and delivering nature-based solutions, and therefore could continue to deliver high-quality interventions under private finance schemes.
- 6) Monitoring data from WRT projects helps to remove barriers around low confidence in NBS to reliably deliver desired outputs. Adding to this weight of evidence increases investor confidence over time.

The examples of **emerging or potential future operations** identified in this map include:

- 1) Operating as a delivery partner within blended finance schemes. Whilst there is some precedent for WRT working as a delivery partner for NBS projects funded by the private sector, this is often linked to one company, rather than a larger consortium of businesses operating in partnership with public sector partners. If a blended finance scheme emerged, WRT would be well placed to operate as a delivery partner.
- 2) Working with emergent ecosystem service markets, such as mandatory Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) and nutrient credits, has required upskilling amongst WRT staff members. Continuing to develop our collective professional skillset to deliver these projects will help to support landowners to profit from credit schemes in the future. Working to pilot nutrient trading in the Southwest has already helped to overcome barriers that ostensibly lower investor confidence, such as novelty, lack of evidence in favour of NBS effectiveness, et cetera.
- 3) Participating in public-private sector partnerships. Whilst WRT already works closely across multiple public-private consortia, developing closer links through project work between industry and the public sector will not only help to mainstream NBS but also support the emergence of a Community Interest Company or Special Purpose Vehicle to deliver at scale. These schemes have emerged elsewhere in the UK, but not yet in the Southwest.

Strategic Alignment

To operationalise emerging and future activities identified in the system map, WRT has sought to strategically align project activities with the wider context of green finance for climate adaptation in Devon and Cornwall. This approach has supported the emergence of the following significant outputs:

- 1) Integration of Systems Thinking approaches into catchment partnerships and catchment management strategies.
- 2) Creation of a business network interested in taking forward climate adaptation finance opportunities.

Box 5.1: Workshops for strategic alignment in the Westcountry Region, UK

1. Systems thinking workshop. In 2024, WRT collaborated with Natural England to co-deliver a series of systems thinking workshops for the Camel Catchment. The purpose of this exercise was not only to identify and prioritise knowledge or delivery gaps to improve the environmental, social, and economic condition of the Camel catchment, but also to develop a scalable systems thinking methodology which could be replicated with other catchment partnerships.

The Camel catchment was chosen as a pilot group due to the relatively small size of the partnership; the presence of TransformAr sites within the catchment, and the high levels of knowledge and expertise held by catchment partners provided an opportunity to co-deliver workshops. The workshops took place during March and September 2024 and were attended by 12 and 13 participants, respectively. Whilst some participants attended both events, repeating the process provided opportunity for reflection and refinement, making the second workshop more effective.

The methodology used was a **Root Cause analysis**. This method was selected for three key reasons:

1. Simplicity, to ensure the process is sufficiently replicable and scalable.
2. To discover key drivers of poor environmental conditions within the catchment
3. Establish consensus on key problems to inform the catchment management strategy

Participants collectively agreed on a common problem within the catchment, and then collaboratively traced contributing factors back to their root causes. The process highlights areas that are well understood as well as existing knowledge gaps. Participants were also encouraged to trace relationships between factors to identify feedback loops and wider dependencies.

Figure 47 Visual representation of Root Cause analysis

The systems maps identified key sectors responsible for discrete types of pollution. For instance, the presence of historic mine waste in the catchment is known to cause metal pollution in waterbodies, however liability for this pollution is complex and poorly understood within the catchment partnership. The full results of this process fall outside the scope of TransformAr, however the resulting methodology was presented during the wider Catchment Partnership meeting with the view to continue revising and evolving the process internally within Natural England. Identifying key industries and stakeholders responsible for poor environmental conditions through a systems thinking approach helps to identify potential beneficiaries of ecosystem services, ultimately contributing to potential business cases.

2. Consultation workshop

Another workshop was organized to attract private sector funding/ investment, based on the idea that greater collaboration between the third sector, public sector, and private sector is required to accelerate investment into NBS for climate change adaptation. To maximise effectiveness, WRT internally completed a stakeholder mapping exercise to prioritise sectors with both high dependency on continuing ecosystem services for their operations, and with whom we have limited prior engagement. This approach helped to diversify engagement, building new relationships with private companies to facilitate successful cross-sector working. As a result, workshop participants enthusiastically consented to being contacted about future opportunities to fund or co-finance NBS in the southwest, highlighting the value of a systems approach to guiding further investment into climate change adaptation.

Consultation Workshop Feedback

- 3 organizations agreed that 'as a result of attending this workshop, I am more likely to pursue involvement in climate adaptation opportunities in future'
- Participants all agreed to receive further communications about opportunities to develop climate adaptation projects
- Participants agreed that the workshop provided a valuable opportunity to get to know new stakeholders, their perspectives, and what they are working on
- Many found the discussions highly valuable, and felt it was a great opportunity for knowledge sharing across sectors

Whilst accelerating the flow of private finance into climate change adaptation measures is difficult in the absence of strong policy and government leadership, analysing organisational roles within regional green finance contexts clarifies areas of influence and opportunities for further exploitation. Systems thinking provides a helpful framework for completing this work, due to the capacity of system maps to simultaneously locate stakeholders, networks and relationships. In highlighting opportunities for organisations to increase influence, either through removing key barriers to private finance or through supporting the development of green finance opportunities, systems maps are key to accelerating the flow of private finance into climate adaptation measures. Furthermore, embedding systems thinking into regional catchment management strategies increases the visibility of ecosystem service beneficiaries, supporting future financialization of nature markets (particularly where responsibility/liability is also clarified). Finally, systems approaches also support organisations to pursue opportunities for cross-sectoral, inter-organisational strategic alignment. In the context of regional finance for NBS, this led to successful exploitation of future private sector partnerships and increased availability of funding/finance for adaptation measures.

6.0 Step 6: Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning

Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (S6) (M&E) are fundamental processes in assessing the effectiveness, sustainability, and scalability of climate adaptation solutions. M&E frameworks enable the tracking of progress, the measurement of direct and indirect impacts, and the support of evidence-based decision-making. This section outlines general steps and tools that organizations can use to design and implement M&E systems, using TransformAr as an example to illustrate practical application.

In TransformAr, M&E efforts systematically evaluate the outcomes of multiple climate adaptation solutions across diverse demonstrator regions. Activities are performed through regular meetings, site visits, video calls, and stakeholder engagement events. Demonstrators integrate a wide range of data collection tools, such as smart sensors, citizen apps, GIS, and satellite imagery, tailored to site-specific indicators. Evaluation frameworks like Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (HILCSA) are used to ensure alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The inclusion of behavioural, governance, and financial innovations (e.g., citizen-science engagement, green bonds, resilience indices) further enhances the replicability and upscaling potential of tested solutions across diverse socio-environmental contexts.

Key components for effective M&E include:

1. Setting up the **monitoring framework**: selecting indicators and setting up methods of data collection and integration.
2. Define **evaluation methodology** and **evaluate**: establishing baseline (reference) conditions, continuous monitoring, and applying both qualitative and quantitative evaluation measures.
3. If transferring or scaling up of the M&E efforts is relevant, **cross-regional comparisons** can be made to learn about **challenges and potentials**.

6.1 Monitoring framework and data collection

An effective M&E framework for adaptation projects integrates multiple data streams and stakeholder inputs to track progress and assess impact. It typically consists of the following components:

- **Indicator selection** aligned with adaptation goals, solution typology, and socio-ecological context of each demonstrator. Example indicators in the TransformAr project are presented in Table 8.
- **Baseline data collection** to define pre-intervention reference points, including hydrological, climatic, ecological, and social conditions.
- **Continuous data gathering** through a combination of automated sensors (e.g., IoT-based water probes), citizen science platforms (e.g., mobile/web apps), and field observations.
- **Data integration and visualization** using GIS platforms, interactive dashboards, and open-access databases to enable real-time decision-making and cross-stakeholder transparency.

Table 8 Key indicators in example demonstrators of TransformAr

Solution Type	Demonstrator Example	Key Indicators
Wetlands restoration	Oristano	Water quality (salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen), flood regulation
Urban green infrastructure	Egaleo	Air temperature, humidity, citizen engagement rates
Stormwater management	Lappeenranta	Water infiltration rate, pollutant load, social acceptance
Aquaculture resilience	Galicia	Shellfish mortality rates, habitat sediment changes
Riparian buffer zones	Westcountry Region	Nutrient loading, biodiversity indices

Box 6.1: Key data collection tools in TransformAr

- **Smart Climate Stations (e.g., Egaleo):** Microclimate monitoring (temperature, humidity, air quality) with public-facing data via citizen app.
- **Water Quality Sensors (e.g., Oristano, Lappeenranta):** Continuous monitoring of parameters such as pH, turbidity, salinity, and dissolved oxygen in stormwater and wetlands.
- **Remote Sensing and GIS (e.g., Galicia):** Mapping land use change, sediment transport, and coastal zone dynamics using drone and satellite imagery.
- **Citizen Surveys & Discrete Choice Experiments (e.g., Lappeenranta, Gjøvik):** Assessing public preferences, willingness to pay, and social acceptance of nature-based solutions

These tools are integrated across demonstrators to support adaptive management, replication potential assessment, and upscaling strategies.

6.2 Evaluation Methodology

Robust M&E methodologies are essential to assess both the immediate effectiveness and the long-term sustainability of climate adaptation interventions. These should incorporate a structured, multi-phase approach:

1. **Baseline Assessment:** Establish environmental, technical, and social reference conditions prior to implementation using historical datasets, surveys, and in-situ measurements.
2. **Continuous Monitoring:** Track biophysical indicators (e.g., water quality, biodiversity), infrastructure performance, and socio-economic co-benefits through sensors, citizen inputs, and periodic reporting.
3. **Mid-term Reviews:** Evaluate interim results and adjust implementation strategies, KPIs, or stakeholder roles accordingly.
4. **Ex-Post Evaluation:** Conducted at project closure to assess systemic impact, replication potential, alignment with SDGs, and lessons learned.

To provide a comprehensive picture, both qualitative and quantitative methods may be used. Evaluation should apply integrated sustainability frameworks such as **HILCSA** (Holistic and Integrated Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment), which merges environmental, economic, and social indicators to produce a **Sustainability Rating Method (SRM)** tailored to each demonstrator’s context.

Box 6.2: M&E examples in TransformAr

Example 1: Monitoring Wetland Restoration in Oristano, Italy

- **Goal:** Improve water quality and enhance flood regulation through nature-based measures.
- **Steps:** Baseline monitoring of sediment and water parameters; installation of **Smart Gate** system to manage water flow; ongoing collection of pH, salinity, and chlorophyll data.
- **Results:** Early monitoring shows better circulation, reduced stagnation, and lower sediment build-up, supporting habitat restoration.

Figure 48 Smart Gate Installation

Example 2: Monitoring Urban Stormwater Management in Lappeenranta, Finland

- **Goal:** Reduce urban flood risk and pollutant loads.
- **Steps:** Installation of a biofiltration system, real-time monitoring of water flow and quality, and citizen app development for awareness.
- **Results:** Improved urban runoff management and increased stakeholder awareness.

Figure 49 Monitoring of Biofiltration site

Example 3: Monitoring Shellfish Aquaculture Resilience in Galicia

- **Goal:** Enhance the adaptive capacity of mussel and clam farming to climate-related stressors such as rising temperatures, sediment shifts, and water quality changes.
- **Steps:** Deployment of **IoT-based monitoring systems** on mussel rafts to collect real-time environmental and hydrodynamic data (e.g., temperature, salinity, wave exposure), **Sediment analysis** and tracking of habitat conditions in intertidal zones, and development of a **Resilience Index** by UVIGO, integrating scientific data and stakeholder input to assess the vulnerability and adaptive readiness of the aquaculture sector.
- **Results:** Improved farm management and early warning for adverse conditions. Strengthened decision-making capacity among producers and policymakers.

6.3 Cross-Regional Comparisons and Best Practices

Cross-regional comparison is a cornerstone of the TransformAr monitoring and evaluation process. It enables shared learning across demonstrators and strengthens the adaptability and scalability of tested solutions. By analysing how different regions implement, monitor, and evaluate similar interventions, the project identifies critical success factors and transferability potential.

Several cross-regional insights were identified. First, on the topic of **financial mechanisms**, the Westcountry Region's "**Delivery Partnerships**" (originally presented as green bonds) showcase how economic intermediaries can aggregate ecosystem services (e.g., nutrient offsets) into bankable packages. This simplifies transactions between landowners and funders and accelerates the implementation of nature-based restoration. Second, in Lappeenranta (Finland), **real-time environmental data** collected via smart sensors and citizen engagement platforms (e.g., CitySen.App) are

directly visualized and made accessible to the public. This enhances transparency, awareness, and responsive decision-making in urban stormwater management. Third, governance models can enable stakeholder engagement. In **Italy and Spain (Oristano and Galicia)**, governance structures such as **Coastal Contracts** and **Living Labs** enabled cross-sectoral coordination among local authorities, fishers, farmers, and conservation actors. These participatory processes improved institutional coherence and project acceptance. Finally, citizen participation can stimulate awareness and acceptance. For instance, in TransformAr, the **Egaleo Smart Climate Solutions (SCS)** and accompanying citizen education programs (AWAR) demonstrate how microclimate monitoring and school engagement can build long-term societal resilience. Data from SCS are visualized through a city-wide IoT infrastructure and used for climate awareness campaigns.

Through systematic comparison of KPIs, stakeholder feedback, and implementation conditions, TransformAr identifies **scalable models**, and highlights **context-specific innovations**.

6.4 Challenges and Future Steps

Despite substantial progress across all TransformAr demonstrators, several challenges persist in implementing robust, scalable, and long-term Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) systems. These issues must be addressed to ensure continuity, replicability, and policy relevance of the adaptation solutions. Moreover, the challenges can serve as useful learning points for potential replicators. The following presents the key challenges and future steps.

Data Gaps & Inconsistencies. Delays in sensor installation, incomplete baseline datasets, and seasonal variability complicate longitudinal assessments. Some demonstrators lacked sufficient time series to confidently measure trends (e.g., wetland sedimentation or aquaculture resilience). Hence, robust baselines need to be established early; prioritize pre-intervention data collection to enable credible before-after comparisons, especially for environmental parameters. In addition, one could implement flexible monitoring schedules that account for seasonal dynamics and emergent challenges (e.g., droughts, infrastructure delays).

Stakeholder Engagement. Sustaining long-term participation of citizens, local authorities, and private actors is difficult, particularly after the pilot or funding phases. Engagement requires continuous feedback loops, co-benefits, and transparency in decision-making. It is recommended to engage stakeholders from the start in M&E co-design and to invest in capacity building (e.g., training on data interpretation, technical tools, and governance feedback).

Integration of New Technologies. While digital tools like IoT sensors, citizen apps, and GIS are increasingly adopted, the full potential of **AI and big data analytics** for predictive modelling and dynamic response planning remains underutilized across demonstrators. Future policymakers and researchers can integrate predictive modelling, anomaly detection, and scenario analysis to improve proactive decision-making and early warning systems.

Contextual Replication Complexity. Successfully adapting a solution (e.g., constructed wetlands, resilience indices) to new social, ecological, or institutional environments requires flexible design and in-depth local co-creation processes. For example, monitoring outcomes should be aligned with governance targets (e.g., SDG indicators), enabling integration into local and EU adaptation strategies.

Resource Constraints. Variability in technical capacity, staffing, and funding across regions limits the ability to implement and maintain advanced monitoring systems at scale. It is recommended to ensure long-term sustainability by developing cost-effective, modular M&E frameworks that can scale with available resources and are resilient to funding fluctuations.

Data Management and Interoperability. Harmonizing data formats and ensuring cross-platform compatibility for real-time integration remains a challenge in a multi-partner environment.

Table 9 presents some key insights derived from various TransformAr demonstrators.

Box 6.3: Example from the Westcountry Region, UK

The Westcountry Rivers Trust (WRT) demonstrator focused on **diffuse agricultural pollution** and **habitat degradation** in catchments vulnerable to **climate-related extremes**, including flash floods and prolonged droughts. Initially, the technical approach centred on **Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW)**. However, this solution proved costly and impractical in the highly fragmented agricultural landscape of the region, due to the difficulty in intercepting widely dispersed pollution sources.

Adaptive Shift in Strategy. Through **early monitoring and stakeholder consultation**, the project team recognized the need to pivot. Instead of centralized ICW infrastructure, the demonstrator adopted a more **flexible and cost-effective solution bundle**, including riparian buffer zones, floodplain wetlands, and multi-functional retention ponds. These nature-based solutions were piloted at smaller scales on multiple farms to test feasibility, measure sediment and nutrient capture efficiency, and evaluate hydrological impacts under variable rainfall conditions.

Monitoring Tools & Methods:

- **Baseline sediment and nutrient loading** assessments were carried out.
- **In-situ water quality sensors** for continuous tracking of nitrate and phosphate levels.
- Use of **remote sensing and land-use GIS layers** to assess vegetative cover and connectivity.
- **Stakeholder workshops** involving farmers and landowners to co-design buffer configurations.

Learning Outcomes. Real-time feedback loops enabled iterative refinement of buffer locations, vegetation types, and intervention sequencing. The example demonstrates the importance of seasonally adaptive management, particularly in flood-prone landscapes with rapid hydrological shifts. WRT developed technical criteria and replicable guidelines for nature-based agricultural runoff solutions under diverse European agroecological conditions.

Broader Contribution to TransformAr:

- Validated the principle that **adaptive, decentralized, and modular solutions** are more viable in certain rural contexts than large-scale engineered interventions.
- The Westcountry experience fed into the **Replication Guide (D5.9)**, offering practical lessons on financing, stakeholder engagement, and multi-site scaling.
- It served as a **testing ground for delivery partnerships**, a financial mechanism later framed in the project as an alternative to green bonds, enabling structured engagement between conservation actors and private buyers of ecosystem credits.

Table 9 Innovation Mapping and Transferable Insights from TransformAr Demonstrators

Demonstrator	Main Focus	Key Innovations	Lessons Learned
Westcountry Region (UK)	Diffuse pollution, flood mitigation via NBS	Adaptive bundles (buffer strips, retention ponds), delivery partnerships	Centralized ICW was unfeasible; modular low-cost NBS more scalable
Egaleo (GR)	Urban microclimate monitoring & education	Smart Climate Stations (SCS), awareness modules (AWAR)	Citizen engagement critical for awareness & data continuity
Lappeenranta (FI)	Urban stormwater management with NBS and citizen app	Biofiltration system, real-time sensors, CitySen app	Integrated digital monitoring improved runoff control & participation
Oristano (IT)	Wetland restoration for flood & water quality	Smart Gates, sediment & salinity monitoring	Early baseline data + hydrological control enhanced restoration
Galicia (ES)	Aquaculture resilience via real-time monitoring	Mussel raft IoT, resilience index, sediment analysis	Cross-sector collaboration vital; real-time data improved readiness

7.0 Exploitation

7.1 Overall

Exploitation means making concrete use of project results to create social, economic, or environmental benefits. This involves transforming research outcomes into practical applications, such as new products, services, processes, or policy recommendations that can be implemented and scaled to address real-world needs. Exploitation is crucial because it ensures that the knowledge and innovations generated by a project do not remain theoretical, but instead deliver tangible value to society, industry, and policymakers, even after the project ends. In collaborative projects, effective exploitation maximizes the impact of research by:

- Enabling commercialization and market uptake of innovations.
- Informing and shaping public policies.
- Supporting further research and development.
- Creating new standards or best practices.

For Horizon 2020 projects, exploitation is a legal obligation and a key criterion for project success. All partners are expected to contribute to the exploitation strategy, identifying stakeholders, analysing market opportunities, and planning how results will be used and sustained beyond the project's lifetime. This approach ensures that public funding leads to broad, long-lasting benefits for science, industry, and society. The exploitation methodology implemented in the TransformAr project follows a structured approach to ensure the identification and production of a plan for protection and market upscale of key exploitable results (KERs). This methodology is designed to be adaptable and replicable in other projects, enabling effective utilization of research outcomes. Below is a step-by-step overview:

1. Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

- Information and results from previous work packages were analysed to identify potential key exploitable results.
- Partners' interests and expected outcomes were collected to establish preliminary exploitation strategies.
- Periodic workshops focused on project Intellectual and Industrial Property (IP) and exploitation of project results facilitated the collection of relevant data and validation of identified KERs.

2. Protection and Benchmarking Analysis

- A detailed benchmarking analysis was conducted, including searches in patent databases, projects, and relevant industry initiatives.
- Intellectual property (IP) protection possibilities were assessed to determine the best strategy for securing innovations.

3. Exploitation Plan Development

- Defined ownership, participating members, and exploitation rights for each KER.
- Conducted a competitive landscape analysis to position project results effectively.

4. Business Model Definition

- Developed commercialization paths and exploitation roadmaps.
- Conducted co-creation sessions with partners to refine commercialization strategies.

5. Implementation and Continuous Monitoring

- A dedicated section for exploitation activities was included in the project's collaborative platform to automate and streamline information collection.
- The Outcomes Form was created to facilitate structured data gathering on technical descriptions, applications, and market potential.
- 1:1 meetings with Work Package Leaders (WPLs) ensured proper data collection and alignment of exploitation strategies.

One of the key examples of Successful Exploitation Activity from TransformAr involved the periodic IP and exploitation workshops. For instance:

- In one of the executed ones, it was possible to define properly the KERs, characterizing their unique value, and updating their societal applications, being able to collect the info needed for Intellectual and Industrial Property Protection and Benchmarking Analysis
- During other executed workshops, an interactive exercise based on the SWOT analysis tool allowed the definition of the target group that helped to refine the market entry strategy and for partner to debate on their outcome potential from an exploitation perspective.

This structured methodology ensures that the research outcomes are effectively protected and successfully brought to the market, serving as a replicable framework for other projects. More detailed information on the methodology can be found on the [TransformAr webpage](https://www.transformar.eu).

7.2 Exploitation Targeted to EC and National Stakeholders Exploitation

In the context of TransformAr, refers to the process of converting project results into concrete applications that generate long-term social, environmental, economic, and policy value. It ensures that EU-funded research leads to transformative impacts across Europe by supporting real-world implementation, scaling of innovations, and policy integration at both European and national levels. This section outlines how the TransformAr project aligns with the European Commission's expectations for result uptake, while also supporting Member State adaptation strategies, national innovation ecosystems, and regional development agendas.

A Strategic Framework for Multilevel Impact

1. The TransformAr exploitation strategy was developed to bridge the gap between research and practice by:
 - Ensuring the transferability of results across local, regional, and national contexts
 - Creating tools and frameworks that are usable by public authorities, regulators, and infrastructure planners
 - Enabling replication and policy adoption through engagement with national agencies, local governments, and thematic networks. The approach is fully aligned with the European Green Deal, the EU Strategy on Climate Adaptation, and supports the implementation of national climate laws, adaptation plans, and resilience-building agendas.

Policy-Driven Exploitation Methodology

TransformAr's exploitation methodology includes five structured steps that ensure results are not only protected and validated, but also made relevant and accessible to policy actors and public implementers:

Step 1: Identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

- All work packages were reviewed to identify outputs with direct relevance to public governance, such as tools for participatory planning, urban resilience systems, ecosystem restoration protocols, and financial mechanisms.
- National and local authorities were involved in reviewing KERs to validate their applicability and alignment with territorial planning needs and national environmental priorities.

Step 2: Protection and Benchmarking

- Legal frameworks and public sector standards were reviewed to ensure compliance and ease of integration of project tools into national digital platforms and climate services.
- Benchmarking included comparison with national pilot projects (e.g., LIFE, Interreg, national adaptation pilots) to ensure added value and interoperability.

Step 3: Development of Targeted Exploitation Plans

For each KER, specific pathways were outlined for:

- EU-level policy integration (e.g., via Climate-ADAPT, Covenant of Mayors, Horizon Europe Missions)
- National-level uptake, including incorporation into National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), river basin plans, coastal zone management strategies, and municipal resilience roadmaps.

- Stakeholder mapping identified national ministries (e.g. environment, climate, interior), regional authorities, municipal networks, water agencies, and energy planning bodies as potential adopters.

Step 4: Public Sector-Oriented Business Models

Business models were adapted to the realities of the public sector, focusing on:

- Public procurement pathways (pre-commercial procurement, green public purchasing).
- Open-source tools and guidance documents to facilitate rapid adoption by municipalities and agencies.
- Collaboration with national digital and geospatial infrastructures to ensure technical alignment.

Step 5: Monitoring, Dialogue, and Feedback Mechanisms

- An internal system was set up to monitor progress on exploitation across governance levels.
- Policy dialogues with national and regional institutions were initiated to gather feedback, facilitate tailoring of tools, and create replication interest.

Tangible Results for Policy Implementation

The following key project outputs have immediate value for both EC and national-level stakeholders:

- Citizen Engagement App: Enables real-time reporting of climate events. Can be adopted by municipalities and linked to national disaster alert systems.
- Resilience Index and Governance Frameworks: Can be integrated into national risk assessment methodologies or used by city networks to benchmark climate preparedness.
- Nature-Based Urban Drainage Systems (NBS): Scalable solutions for flood control and urban greening; eligible for funding under EU cohesion policy and national infrastructure plans.
- Digital Monitoring Systems: Open and low-cost tools for water quality and stormwater tracking—ideal for regional water authorities or basin management plans.
- Financial Mechanisms: Tools such as green bonds, adaptation credits, and investment-readiness models that support national public and blended finance initiatives.

Opportunities for National Stakeholder Engagement and Support

To amplify the project's impact, TransformAr calls on national stakeholders—ministries, development banks, agencies, and regional governments—to:

Endorse and adopt project tools within their existing programs and plans (e.g., NAPs, smart cities agendas, flood management strategies).

Support replication through regional funding instruments or partnerships (e.g., using Just Transition or Recovery and Resilience Facility funds).

Contribute to capacity-building efforts, such as national training seminars or integration into public sector curricula.

Promote uptake via national research and innovation ecosystems, ensuring continued evolution and contextualization of the results.

Forward-looking Recommendations for EC and Member States For the European Commission:

- Use TransformAr tools and insights to inform Horizon Europe Missions, especially those addressing climate-neutral cities, climate adaptation, and ocean/coastal resilience.

- Promote KERs via the Climate-ADAPT platform and consider incorporating selected outputs into Joint Research Centre knowledge repositories.
- Include TransformAr as a reference case in future calls for cross-sectoral innovation in adaptation and urban resilience. For Member States:
- Integrate TransformAr outputs into national and regional planning processes as part of NAP implementation and decentralized adaptation governance.
- Explore institutional partnerships for further development and scaling of pilot-tested tools.
- Leverage existing funding programmes (e.g., LIFE, European Structural and Investment Funds) to replicate KERs in other regions. In closure, TransformAr presents a policy-relevant, scalable, and well-structured exploitation model that supports both EU-level objectives and Member State needs. Its tools, methodologies, and outcomes are designed not only for scientific excellence, but for public good, institutional uptake, and systemic transformation. With continued support and collaboration, the project can serve as a cornerstone for Europe's ongoing efforts in building climate resilience across all levels of governance.

8.0 Discussion and Conclusion

The aims of this report are to consolidate the work done within the TransformAr project, and to provide a guide for future decision-makers and implementers to use the developed and applied tools and methods. These tools and methods were discussed following the steps of the climate adaptation process according to the EU Mission's [Regional Adaption Support Tool](#) (RAST): (1) Preparing the ground for adaptation, (2) Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities, (3) Identifying adaptation options, (4) Assessing and selection adaptation options, (5) Implementing adaptation policies and actions, and (6) Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning. Step by step, the relevant methods used and developed by TransformAr were described, providing examples from the actionable solutions that were implemented in the project's demonstrators (Lappeenranta, Finland; West Country Region, UK; Guadeloupe, France; Galicia, Spain; Oristano, Italy; Egaleo, Greece) and one replicator (Gjøvik, Norway). The combination of the steps and actionable solutions is called 'Innovation Packages', i.e., this report.

An overview of the steps, applicable methods, tools, TransformAr reports (deliverables) and key learnings is provided in Table 10. Concludingly, there are 4 **key learnings** that appeared in multiple steps: the importance and challenges of stakeholder engagement, context-specific and flexible approaches, data collection and integration, and capacity and resources.

Co-innovation through stakeholder engagement is a specific objective of the TransformAr project. Involving stakeholders is not only important when laying the groundwork for adaptation (step 1), but throughout all the steps. For instance, ex-ante assessments of solutions (step 4) require the involvement of experts to gather the correct data (e.g., cost data), and sustained financing is more likely when private, public and third sector investors are involved. TransformAr organized workshops and interviews at several stages to ensure the right stakeholders were involved and engaged, for instance while co-defining the adaptation pathways through a variety of sessions (i.e., the [Playbook](#)) (step 3), or when interviewing financial institutions to analyse bankability (step 6). Also, the implementation of certain solutions requires a dedicated team on the ground (e.g., maintaining sensors or nature-based solutions), most likely a collaboration between public and private sector efforts (step 6). TransformAr's [guidelines for stakeholder engagement](#) and [Playbook](#) are useful tools for engaging stakeholders and co-creating adaptation pathways. While stakeholders were successfully engaged in many stages of the adaptation process, a **key challenge** was longer-term participation of citizens, local authorities and private actors after pilot or funding phases. Stakeholder fatigue is common and maintaining engagement through continuous feedback, co-benefits and transparency in decision-making is recommended. Creating adaptation solutions that are cross-sectoral can help to keep stakeholders involved. At the same time, one should be wary of over-soliciting stakeholders, which can also cause fatigue. This can be prevented by setting clear goals and plans, and optimizing the time of everyone involved.

A second key learning is about **context-specific and flexible approaches**. Throughout multiple steps, it was realized that tools and methods (e.g., socio-economic assessments of solutions) need to be streamlined so they can be applied across regions and countries, while also being flexibly adaptable to local circumstances. For instance, while preparing the ground for adaptation (step 1), knowledge of the local context and governance structure is needed to guide stakeholder co-innovation meetings, and specific communication strategies and levels of involvement may be needed to guide the process. On top of that, tools for socio-economic assessment, such as the Nature Smart Cities Business Model, work well when comparing solutions within a certain context, but not yet to compare across regions. These tools could also benefit from being more adaptable to the local context (e.g., adjusting prices). On the other hand, TransformAr's tools to evaluate solutions, such as the [Transformational Adaptation Scorecard](#) and

the [Sustainability Rating Method](#) are more readily comparable across locations, but do not lead to rigorous quantitative outcomes and do not study all topics simultaneously (e.g., economic, social, environmental, sustainability, transformational...). Hence, we recommend future investigators to develop rigorous methods to streamline holistic assessments of adaptation solutions, while being easily adaptable to the local context through inputting local data. A final, but crucial, example is that the adaptation solutions to be implemented need to be adapted to the local context to address the most pressing needs and challenges, while also considering public acceptance, resources and capacity.

Third, an important learning is the importance of **collecting and integrating relevant data**. While aiming to evaluate and compare solutions before and after implementation, partners repeatedly stumbled upon the lack of available data and data integration. Local authorities that plan and implement adaptation solutions may lack the expertise and capacity to collect relevant data, such as precise costs and environmental impacts, and track those in an integrated system. For instance, local economic data is needed to feed into field-applicable risk assessments (step 2: assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities), and also throughout the ex-ante assessments (step 4: assessing and selection adaptation options), demonstrators often did not possess all the necessary data to conduct socio-economic or sustainability assessments. Early-on selection of baselines and indicators, while keeping track of the necessary data is also essential for proper monitoring and evaluation (step 6). Digital and technological solutions, such as the ones implemented in TransformAr (e.g., Stormwater, Intertidal and Mussel-raft monitoring), contribute to the collection of detailed data collection in streamlined systems. It is recommended that adaptation planning teams identify the data needed for evaluation and set up appropriate systems as early as possible, while continuously updating and monitoring these efforts. The tools and methods described in these Innovation Packages can provide a guide to which data could be important at what stage.

Finally, it is crucial to consider the **available resources and capacity** and adjust adaptation plans accordingly. All steps of the adaptation process require dedicated teams of appropriate stakeholders, experts, policymakers, investors and workers in the field (to implement and maintain solutions). Planners and implementers should consider all steps of the adaptation process and regard this as an ongoing process that does not stop after implementation. For example, maintenance, monitoring and evaluation are needed to ensure continuous positive impacts and learning. Hence, it is advised to be realistic about the local capacity in terms of manpower, expertise and financial resources and adapt plans accordingly. In addition, innovative funding schemes, such as TransformAr's local adaptation fund in Guadeloupe or workshops with potential investors, can help to expand capacity.

Our five adaptation solution categories align with a recent report by the European Environment Agency (2024), namely governance and institutional measures, economic instruments and finance, physical and technological measures, nature-based solutions and knowledge and behavioural change. The report highlights what enables climate adaptation actions: sustained political commitment, good governance, sharing of good practice and peer-learning, citizen engagement, effective use and knowledge and data, and sustained funding. All of these are integrated within TransformAr's learnings and challenges, summarized above. Finally, the European Environment Agency (2024) emphasizes the need for the incorporation of social justice in climate action, and for more quantitative evidence of adaptation solutions, both of which did not get prominent attention throughout the TransformAr project. Future projects should aim to incorporate social justice (e.g., by involving vulnerable groups in the decision-making process) and generate more robust and generalizable evidence of solutions.

These Innovation Packages consolidate most of the work done in TransformAr and provide a toolbox for future researchers and implementers of adaptation solutions. Jointly with other research and

implementation projects and efforts organized by the European Union and regional/local authorities, we hope to have provided relevant groundwork for future efforts, and consequently to have contributed to a more climate change-resilient continent.

Table 10 Key methods, tools and learnings per step

	Methods	Tools	Deliverables	Key Learnings
Step 1: Preparing the ground for adaptation	Co-innovation process: stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder Engagement Guidelines and Mapping	D1.1 D1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder fatigue should be prevented by planning for bundled activities, flexible reporting, joint decision-making and tailored follow-ups. Adapt methods to context: demonstrators required custom governance structures, communication methods and engagement strategies. Stakeholder matrices and maps should be re-evaluated and updated as a project evolves, so they stay relevant.
		Best Practices for Stakeholder Management	D1.4 D1.5 D1.6 D1.7 D1.3	
Step 2: Assessing climate risk and vulnerabilities	Integrated Climate Risk Assessment	Climate Impacts Online Europe	D2.1 D2.2 D2.3 D2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current economic analyses often focus on select impact chains, but a more comprehensive assessment—including health, agriculture, and water scarcity—is needed to capture the full scope of climate effects. Linking climate and economic models is complex due to differing methodologies and data limitations, especially at the sub-national level; clear protocols are essential for effective integration. Economic models struggle to reflect field-based, local solutions. One should aim to collect data representing community-level economic interdependencies. The creation of risk indexes that relate (projected) climatic variables with socio-economic variables can be challenging as one should account for non-linearities.
	Climate Risk Indices		D2.5 D2.6	
Step 3: Identifying adaptation options	Pathway co-construction through stakeholder workshops	Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook	D3.10 D3.3 D3.9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Involve enough and diverse stakeholders, while at the same time avoiding over-solicitation by concisely identifying objectives and steps. Time management and optimization is necessary. The defined actions should be tangible and cutting across sectors. Align the process across contexts to enhance impact and coherence.
	Adaptation planning through stakeholder workshops	Toolkit for Adaptive Action Planning	D3.7 D3.8 D3.9 D3.2	

Step 4: Assessing and selecting adaptation options	Discrete Choice Experiments for Public Acceptance	/	D6.1 D5.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ex-ante assessments require a team of people with the right expertise (management, climate change adaptation, urban planning, ...). Decision-makers and implementers should preferably gather and keep track of cost and urban planning data to feed into assessments of solutions. A comprehensive assessment before selection requires a variety of methods to include dimensions of sustainability, environmental impacts, costs, benefits, social and cultural impacts, avoided damages, and the extent to which the solution is transformational. Simultaneously, it is advised that methods are streamlined across regions and projects so that cross-comparisons are possible.
	Assessment of avoided damages	Avoided damages and benefits tool	D3.4 D3.5	
	Assessment of how transformative a solution/ pathway is	Transformational Adaptation Scorecard	D6.4	
	Ex-ante impact assessment	Nature Smart Cities – Business Model <i>(not developed by TransformAr)</i>	D3.6	
	Sustainability assessment of pathways	Sustainability Rating Method	D5.2 D5.9	
	Energy modelling	The Global Energy System Model – GENeSYS-MOD <i>(not developed by TransformAr)</i>	/	
Step 5: Implementing adaptation policies and actions	Implementation	Learning stories and catalogue of solutions	D4.1 D4.2 D4.3 D4.4 D4.5 D6.3 D7.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certain solutions require a dedicated team on the ground to support implementation and engagement (e.g., sensors, ...) Regarding awareness campaigns, long-term commitment to climate education and ongoing collaborations are needed for success. The success and maintenance of governance schemes require stakeholder engagement, data accessibility and informed decision-making, administrative capacity and experience, and institutional support and local ownership. For long-term success, Nature-Based Solutions require data availability and integration, coordination stakeholder engagement and financial mechanisms. Digital solutions (e.g., monitoring systems) foster collaboration between researchers and local stakeholders, and can provide detailed data.
	Assessment of replicability potential	Replicability Assessment Tool	D4.6	
	Bankability interviews	/	D5.3 D5.5	
	Systems thinking and strategic alignment workshops	/	D5.6	

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative financial models are needed to support solutions (e.g., local adaptation fund). • Solutions need to be tailored to the context's needs and challenges. • Evidence on the monetary revenue potential of solutions and the importance of governance support is needed to obtain more funding. • Cooperation between third sector, public and private investors is needed to accelerate investment.
Step 6: Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning	Monitoring & Evaluation Methodology	/	D5.8 D5.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robust baselines and data collections, and the possibility of data harmonization and integration need to be established early-on to ensure proper monitoring. • To sustain long-term participation of stakeholders, continuous feedback loops, co-benefits and transparency are needed. • In the future, implementers and researchers can work on leveraging the full potential of AI and big data analytics for predictive modelling and response planning. • The context is important: replicating a solution in another context requires a flexible design and co-creation processes (e.g., adaption to local governance targets). • Variability in technical capacity, staffing, and funding across regions limits the ability to implement and maintain advanced monitoring systems at scale. Implementing modular M&E frameworks that can adapt depending on resources is recommended.

References

- Barani, M., Löffler, K., Garibashvili, L. and Del Granado, P.C. 2025. The road to a sustainable energy system in the Guadeloupe archipelago: Challenges and opportunities. *Heliyon*.
- Brown, H.L., Bos, D.G., Walsh, C.J., Fletcher, T.D. and RossRakesh, S. 2016. More than money: how multiple factors influence householder participation in at-source stormwater management. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management* 59(1), 79-97.
- Buckell, J., Buchanan, J., Wordsworth, S., Becker, F., Morrell, L., Roope, L., Kaur, A. and Abel, L. 2020. Hypothetical Bias. In: *Catalogue of Bias*.
- Chhetri, N., Stuhlmacher, M. and Ishtiaque, A. 2019. Nested pathways to adaptation. *Environmental Research Communications* 1(1), 015001.
- Colombo, S., Budziński, W., Czajkowski, M. and Glenk, K. 2022. The relative performance of ex - ante and ex - post measures to mitigate hypothetical and strategic bias in a stated preference study. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 73(3), 845-873.
- Cools, J., Bjørnåvold, A., Fabri, C., Zorita, S., Castellani, C., Breil, M., Johnson, K.S., Sedlar, M., Simonet, S., Pérez-Blanco, D., Perdih, T.S., Lourenço, T.C., Peinhardt, K., Schmidt, G. and Goicolea-Güemez, E. 2025. Understanding Transformational Adaptation: A Shared Vision Across EU Horizon Projects. Projects' policy brief under the EU Mission on adaptation to climate change's implementation platform (MIP4Adapt). .
- Deubelli, T.M. and Mechler, R. 2021. Perspectives on transformational change in climate risk management and adaptation. *Environmental Research Letters* 16(5), 053002.
- EIP-AGRI 2017. Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects.
- European Commission 2021. Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2021-2024).
- European Environment Agency 2024. Urban adaptation in Europe: what works?
- Fedele, G., Donatti, C.I., Harvey, C.A., Hannah, L. and Hole, D.G. 2019. Transformative adaptation to climate change for sustainable social-ecological systems. *Environmental Science & Policy* 101, 116-125.
- Green, O.O., Shuster, W.D., Rhea, L.K., Garmestani, A.S. and Thurston, H.W. 2012. Identification and induction of human, social, and cultural capitals through an experimental approach to stormwater management. *Sustainability* 4(8), 1669-1682.
- Haab, T., Lewis, L.Y. and Whitehead, J. 2020. State of the art of contingent valuation. *Oxford research encyclopedia of environmental science*.
- Haoran, Y., Bjornavold, A., Du-Ikonen, L., Van Passen, S. and Cools, J. 2025. Are citizens willing to take action on stormwater management? Adapting to climate change in Finland and Norway. [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- IPCC 2022. Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- Johnston, R.J., Boyle, K.J., Adamowicz, W., Bennett, J., Brouwer, R., Cameron, T.A., Hanemann, W.M., Hanley, N., Ryan, M. and Scarpa, R. 2017. Contemporary guidance for stated preference studies. *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists* 4(2), 319-405.
- Kasdan, M., Kuhl, L. and Kurukulasuriya, P. 2021. The evolution of transformational change in multilateral funds dedicated to financing adaptation to climate change. *Climate and Development* 13(5), 427-442.
- Lieberherr, E. and Green, O.O. 2018. Green infrastructure through citizen stormwater management: Policy instruments, participation and engagement. *Sustainability* 10(6), 2099.

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- Löffler, K., Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Oei, P.-Y., Kemfert, C. and Von Hirschhausen, C. 2017. Designing a model for the global energy system—GENeSYS-MOD: an application of the open-source energy modeling system (OSeMOSYS). *Energies* 10(10), 1468.
- Scolobig, A., Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Pelling, M., Martin, J.G., Deubelli, T.M., Liu, W. and Oen, A. 2023. Transformative adaptation through nature-based solutions: a comparative case study analysis in China, Italy, and Germany. *Regional Environmental Change* 23(2), 69.
- UNHR 2024 UN experts urge France to guarantee safe drinking water in Guadeloupe.
- Van Oijstaeijen, W., Van Passel, S. and Cools, J. 2020. Urban green infrastructure: A review on valuation toolkits from an urban planning perspective. *Journal of environmental management* 267, 110603.
- Werners, S.E., Wise, R.M., Butler, J.R., Totin, E. and Vincent, K. 2021. Adaptation pathways: A review of approaches and a learning framework. *Environmental Science & Policy* 116, 266-275.
- Zandvoort, M., Campos, I.S., Vizinho, A., Penha-Lopes, G., Lorencová, E.K., van der Brugge, R., van der Vlist, M.J., van den Brink, A. and Jeuken, A.B. 2017. Adaptation pathways in planning for uncertain climate change: Applications in Portugal, the Czech Republic and the Netherlands. *Environmental Science & Policy* 78, 18-26.

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

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